

July 2025

**Cross-cutting activity 1:
Support to the generation and
the development of start-ups
and spin-offs**

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Table of contents

INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES	3
RESULTS	4
ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS	11
NEXT STEPS	12
1. SPOKE 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1	13
1.1. SPOKE 1 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	13
1.2. SPOKE 1 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	13
1.3. SPOKE 1 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	14
1.4. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	14
1.5. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	14
References	14
2. SPOKE 2 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1	15
2.1. SPOKE 2 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	15
2.2. SPOKE 2 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	17
2.3. SPOKE 2 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	19
2.4. SPOKE 2 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	20
2.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	20
2.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	20
References	22
3. SPOKE 3 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1	23
3.1. SPOKE 3 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	23
3.2. SPOKE 3 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	23
3.3. SPOKE 3 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	29
3.4. SPOKE 3 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	30
3.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	31
3.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	31
4. SPOKE 4 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1	32
4.1. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	32
4.2. SPOKE 4 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	33
4.3. SPOKE 4 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	37

4.4. SPOKE 4 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	39
4.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	40
4.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	41
5. SPOKE 5 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1	42
5.1. SPOKE 5 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	42
5.2. SPOKE 5 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	43
5.3. SPOKE 5 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	55
5.4. SPOKE 5 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	56
5.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	58
5.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	59
6. SPOKE 6 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1	62
6.1. SPOKE 6 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	62
6.2. SPOKE 6 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	63
6.3. SPOKE 6 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	66
6.4. SPOKE 6 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	66
6.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	67
6.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	68
References	68
7. SPOKE 7 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1	69
7.1. SPOKE 7 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	69
7.2. SPOKE 7 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	69
7.3. SPOKE 7 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	70
7.4. SPOKE 7 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	70
7.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	71
8. SPOKE 8 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1	72
8.1. SPOKE 8 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	72
8.2. SPOKE 8 CC1 TASKS AND ONGOING ACTIVITIES	73
8.3. SPOKE 8 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	83
8.4. SPOKE 8 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	83
8.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	84
8.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	85
9. SPOKE 9 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1	86
9.1. SPOKE 9 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW	86
9.2. SPOKE 9 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES	87
9.3. SPOKE 9 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES	91
9.4. SPOKE 9 CC1 MAIN RESULTS	92
9.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN	93
9.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES	94
References	94

INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES

This introduction provides a **comprehensive overview** of the progress of the Cross-cutting activity 1, starting from a **task completion** status summary table, then going task by task through the overall **results** and finally addressing the main **encountered problems, corrective actions** and **next steps**.

The introduction is followed by 9 reports, each offering a detailed perspective from one of the Spokes.

iNEST CC1 goal is to develop a feasible and functional framework, to support the generation and development of start-ups and spin-offs in the North-East of Italy ecosystem. The CC1 tasks (Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration, Fundraising) help academic and guiding research institutions interact among themselves and with the regional context, with the ultimate goal to contribute to regional development through continuous exchange and synergic on-the-field work. Therefore, within this picture, for the design implementation of an innovation ecosystem - functional for the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs -, it is considered strategic to enable the development of these cross-cutting CC1 tasks, that deeply involve all Spokes.

A sum-up of iNEST CC1 **tasks status** as of July 2025 is provided in the following table:

Task	Leader	Sub-Task	Round1	Round2
Task CC1.1 Planning and validation	UniVE	Sub Task CC1.1.1: Planning of CC1 activities		✓
		Sub Task CC1.1.2: Analysis of successful practices	✓	✓
		Sub Task CC1.1.3: Data elaboration		ongoing
	IUAV	Sub Task CC1.1.4: Event and Communication	✓ Selection Day (Mar24) ✓ Demo Day (Oct24) ✓ OI Day (Jan25)	✓ Selection Day (Dec24) ✓ Demo Day (Jun25) □ Final event (Sept25)
Task CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration	UniVE	Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engag. and training of the Key Actors		
		Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implement. of the Scouting Stage	✓	✓
		Sub Task CC1.2.3: Online Entrepreneurial training		
UniUD	Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities	✓ OI Day: 30/01/2025	Mar25-Sept25 (interviews)	
Task CC1.3 Acceleration	UniVR	Sub Task CC1.3.1: Dev. of the Key St. Elements	✓	✓
		Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engag. and coord. of the Key Actors	✓	✓
		Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acc. phase	✓	✓
Task CC1.4 Fundraising	UniTS e PTAA	Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Network		✓
		Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation VC-Invested Stage	Ongoing (May25-Sept25)	
	UniPD	Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage	ongoing support (from June25) + final event in Sept25	

The tasks status can be described as follows:

- **CC1.1: Planning and validation:** planning for round 2 was completed in December 2024. Data elaboration and validation will be done till the end of the project.
- **CC1.2: Pre-Acceleration:** completed 1st (Nov 2023 - March 2024) and 2nd (June - Dec 2024) Pre-Acceleration rounds. Completed research phase of the Open Innovation subTask and first engagement of companies through the OI Day (30/01/2024). OI interviews phase is still running, targeted on a shortlist of the identified companies, to cultivate corporate relationships

and match innovation trajectories of the entrepreneurial ecosystem with academic startups / spin-offs themes.

- **CC1.3: Acceleration:** 1st Acceleration round implemented (April - October 2024), completed review and improvement of the Acceleration Framework for 2nd round; Key Actors engaged for both rounds; completed implementation of the 2nd Acceleration round (Jan - June 2025).
- **CC1.4: Fundraising:** the Task leader (UniTS, PAA) elaborated and proposed a work plan in August 2024 (including: short training on financing and contracts ABC; meetings with banks; “speed date” meetings with different types of investors; external consulting for startup evaluation and 1:1 support in the path to fundraising and investor approaching).

As of July 2025 public procedures were closed for all of the planned initiatives and the implementation has started, with the cycle of trainings and meetings involving banking actors, business angels and traditional investors. The initiatives are being offered in parallel for startups of the 1st and 2nd Acceleration round. The organisation of speed-date meetings with potential industrial partners and the creation of a web-app platform for “High Potential Showroom and Venture Capitalist Platform” are underway and supervised by Spoke 8.

Within the initiatives for the “Sustainable stage” (leader: UniPD) a “Legal sanity check” desk/service has been activated (on request). An additional investor contact activity has been planned by UniPD to reinforce the Sub Task CC1.4.3 (“Design of the Sustainable Stage”). A final event has also been planned for the 18th of September 2025 in Trieste.

RESULTS

Concerning outputs, a comprehensive sum-up of overall **results** achieved as of July 2025 is:

within the CC1.1 Planning and validation

- **Data elaboration (CC1.1.3):** an analysis of the applications to the CC1 program was conducted (using data of both rounds) to address two research questions: 1) *Which persons / teams and which projects was the CC1 able to attract and engage?*; 2) *Who was selected for acceleration? Which factors proved determinant?*. A mix of descriptive statistics, bivariate association tests and logistic regression was employed for the elaboration. Data collection is currently ongoing in relation to a third research question addressing the effectiveness of the Acceleration program: a survey was designed to investigate the progress and “success” of the accelerated teams. The findings from these analyses will be incorporated into a final report due by year-end.

within the CC1.2 Pre-Acceleration task and subtasks

- **Development of the Pre-Acceleration framework:** the previously designed scouting system of iNEST CC1 - providing a common strategy, a standard process and shared tools to the 9 Spokes, while enabling customised implementations according to each Spoke peculiarities - was further improved under guidance of the Program Leader and Scouting Officer. For the 2nd round a stronger focus was on targeted scouting efforts (“hunting”), addressing peculiar research groups. Guidelines for patent analysis and for researchers’ funded projects analysis were developed. Key actors have access to an online repository where all the common documents, minutes and tools are progressively shared and stored.
- **Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (CC1.2.1):** after the initial engagement and training of the Scouting Specialists, and after the individual (almost weekly) coordination of the 1st round, all the Spokes have been continuously involved all together as a unique team during the 2nd round, with periodic monthly meetings (up to the Selection Day - December 3rd 2025) to discuss and review strategies, tools, activities progress, issues and results. The Scouting Specialists, by working in close relationship with the pre-accelerated teams, generated a deep knowledge base that proved to be helpful in the following phases

(Acceleration): some of the Specialists became *de facto* coaches / mentors of the startup projects.

- **Implementation of the Scouting Stage to develop entrepreneurship from the universities' ecosystems and drive the research efforts towards a proof-of-concept (CC1.2.2):** for both rounds the engagement of the target groups proceeded in a decentralized way, with each Spoke collecting ideas from students, researchers and early stage startups (third mission and others linked to universities) using a custom approach, and in synergy with the internal initiatives led by Technology Transfer and IP Valorization.

For the 2nd round the engagement mechanisms (events, calls for ideas, targeted meetings and communication activities) were reinforced with desk analyses of patents and funded projects within each University. Data collection tools and templates were further optimised and centralised (to ease post process data analysis). The funnel structure was maintained, as well as the evaluation criteria, but the contribution of an External Jury was added to the 2nd Selection Day evaluation procedure (60% weight on final score for CCI Committee, 40% weight for External Jury).

The **target n.** of applications to the Open Call was 100+ for each round (min 10 per Spoke) and the actual number of applications / ideas / early stage start-ups collected and their progression towards the Acceleration program was:

Pre-Acc. funnel stage	Round 1	Round 2
Open Call	179	170
Selection Form submission	66	73
CCI Committee evaluation	40	41
Selection Day	32	30
Admission into Acceleration	16	16

The Pre-acceleration process is schematised as follows:

- **Implementation of the basic online entrepreneurial training to provide a standardized model through the ecosystem (CC1.2.3):** open access international benchmarks of entrepreneurial education have been reviewed, after a selection, and then made available to the Spokes in a common shared online space. All the applicants have access to online entrepreneurial learning materials. The chosen benchmark for the learning objects is Stanford business school: <https://startupclass.samaltman.com>. Key themes of the online publicly available lessons are: how to get started, how to raise money, how to build products, and how to grow. Further custom learning objects to train the applicants on the preparation of a Pitch Deck were finalised in a step-by-step [video guide](#) released by the Program Leader, Prof. Carlo Bagnoli." A venture building documentation repository for deepening uses was set-up too.
- **Open innovation activities (CC1.2.4):** the Open Innovation Manager performed a [mapping and classification](#) of innovation oriented companies in the North East, using a Pavitt set of indicators (defined with the support of the Program Leader and of Spoke 2 - UniTN) to select 40 innovative companies from the northeastern ecosystem. The 1st [Open Innovation Day](#) took place on January 30th, 2025, in Padua, where the iNEST project was presented to a wide audience and a prize was consigned to the 40 identified innovative companies. To further explore these companies' current, past, and future innovation trajectories from a qualitative perspective, a series of semi-structured interviews was launched to the CEOs and CTOs. The interviews were designed and proposed in a videoconference format to gather in-depth insights that would complement the initial quantitative selection. For the proceeding of this process towards the matching of the companies to the CC1 accelerated startups, also taking into account the Macro themes, the series of interviews with some of the companies began in May 2025 and is ongoing till September 2025.

within the CC1.3 Acceleration task and subtasks

- **Development of the Key Standardized Elements:** an [Acceleration Framework](#) was developed for the 1st round and with a learning-by-doing approach optimised for the 2nd round: a standardized "educational model" is provided through a centralised program based on itinerant workshops. The [2nd round framework](#), also based on the collected feedback, is characterised by a higher number of workshops (from 6 to 8) with reduced theory content and more practical work for building a solid strategic document ("strategic plan") at the basis of the pitch. The software "[Accelerator App](#)" was implemented for more efficient work tracking, knowledge sharing, pace-keeping and reporting.
- **Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors:** the [Acceleration management team](#) was consolidated with the lead of UniTN (supported by HiT) and UniVR, and benefitted from the continuous contribution of the Scouting Officer, Assistant Scouting Officer and Communication team. Concerning the [coaching system](#), the model was reinforced for the 2nd round, assigning to each startup 1 "expert/senior coach" bringing vertical expertise and 1 "operative coach" offering weekly 1h-meetings to better assist the cofounders throughout all the program. Based on competencies and commitment, some of the [Scouting Specialists](#) were also involved in the "operative coach" role. Throughout the entire duration of the 1st and 2nd Acceleration programs the management team met with regular weekly frequency. Coach coordination meetings were held every other week.
- **Implementation of the Acceleration phase:** the [1st round](#) of the program was offered to 16 startups and completed by 11 of them. Towards the end of the 1st Acceleration program, some of the startups received a spontaneous interest from a number of different investors (such as: industrial, corporate and institutional funds and ventures, incubators, and even private

equities). Therefore, 6 startups were guided by an Acceleration task force in the development of key documents to strengthen their preparedness for dialoguing with investors.

The 2nd round of the program was offered to 15 startups. For this cycle two intermediate cut-offs with a multifaceted jury (academic and investors) were introduced to filter out of the program those teams that initially did not have the right commitment or that were not ready to complete the work required for a good performance at the Demo Day.

All the teams successfully passed the 1st cut-off, even if a third of the cohort received a lower evaluation and was strongly advised to increase the effort in the upcoming part of the program. The output of the 2nd cut-off was the generation of a specific subset of "Early stage projects" with a lower maturity. The 3 teams in this category did not compete for the final prizes. For the composition of the external jury of the 2nd Demo Day, several actors - both public and private - of the Italian startup investors ecosystem were engaged and demonstrated interest in the presented batch of projects. The jury included representatives of: CDP Venture Partners, Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Invitalia, MITO Technology, Obloo Ventures, VeniSIA.

The evaluation procedure included an internal evaluation (completed by the coaches, weighing 60% weight on the final score) and the external evaluation (Demo Day jury, 40% weight). The internal set of evaluation criteria was derived from the selection criteria used in Pre-Acceleration by slightly reviewing the relative weights and adding the criterion n. 11 related to the Go to market / Action plan. The resulting set is the following:

- 15% 1. Problem identification & relevance
- 15% 2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit
- 5% 3. Solution novelty
- 5% 4. Intellectual Property (IP) Protection
- 5% 5. Social and Environmental Impact
- 10% 6. Addressable market
- 5% 7. Market Competitiveness and Positioning
- 15% 8. Team Commitment and Execution Capability
- 5% 9. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
- 10% 10. Operating model scalability
- 10% 11. Go to market / Action plan

The simplified, on-the-field usable set of criteria used by the external jury was the following:

- 30% 1. Investibility
- 20% 2. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
- 30% 3. Team Commitment and potential Execution Capability
- 20% 4. Gut feeling.

In both cases each criterion was defined on a five levels scale, adding up to a maximum final score of 100 points.

The contents of the workshops are reported in the following scheme (for round 2) and in the summary table for both rounds with indication of the workshop location:

Workshops

WS1 – Introduction

Objective: Framing the path and documents to be produced.
Content: Case studies and starting the strategic plan.

WS2 – Problem, Solution and Proposition

Objective: Analysing the problem and defining the proposal.
Content: Mapping problems, existing solutions and value proposition

WS3 – Market & Competition

Objective: Assessing the market and competitive positioning.
Content: Market analysis, competitors and positioning.

Intermediate and final **Pitch clinic**
 for admission to Demo Day

Demo Day

WS4 – Governance, Vision and Strategy

Objective: Aligning vision, mission and strategy.
Content: Creating the Canvas.

WS6 – Action Plan & Eco-Fin

Objective: Planning activities and the financial model.
Content: Action plan and initial economic and financial plan.

WS7 – Eco-Fin & Funding

Objective: Finalising the financial plan and fundraising.
Content: Financial strategy and pitch preparation.

ROUND 1

Date (2024)	Location	Sprint #	Workshop title
19-20 April	UNITS	1	Governance, Mission, Vision, Strategy and Business Model
			Problem and potential customer
10-11 May	UNIPD	2	Solution, value proposition and product POC
			Market, competitors and potential competitive positioning
31 May and 1 June	UniTN - Sol	3	Pitch session test Profit Model
5-6 July	SISSA	4	Operational model
			Economic-financial model
30-31 August	IUAV	5	Fundraising
			Company constitution and corporate governance
20 September	UNIVR	6	Pitch clinic
25 October	UNIVR	-	Demo Day

ROUND 2

Date (2025)	Location	Sprint #	Workshop title
17-18 January	UNITN	1	Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan
7-8 February	UNIVR	2	Problem, actual solution and proposal
28 Feb and 1 March	UNIUD	3	Market and competition
14-15 March	UNIVE	4	Governance, mission & vision, strategy, business model; tools for AI
4 April	IUAV	5	Pitch clinic #1
cut-off			
9-10 May	UNIBZ	6	Action plan & Eco-Fin Plan
23-24 May	UNITS	7	Eco-Fin Plan & funding
6 June	UNIVR	8	Pitch clinic #2
cut-off			
26 June	UNIVE	-	Demo Day

For the 1st round a cycle of 5 webinars was also offered (Presentation of psychological types; Marketing, customer acquisition, sales; IP strategy; Data protection; Legal issues - Shareholders' agreements, term sheets, investment agreements) but revealed low interest and impact.

Satisfaction surveys were periodically administered to the participant teams to assess and adapt the Acceleration program structure and features. A survey was also administered to the coaches, asking them to indicate if there were any topics, not covered in the programme, whose exploration would be beneficial for their assigned teams. As some of the emerging topics were potentially addressable throughout the fundraising phase (either in the workshops or in the 1-1 consultancy meetings), the themes were reported to the Leader (Spoke 8) of the CC1.4 Task, in order to possibly take them into account when planning and implementing activities for the Fundraising phase.

The most relevant supplementary topics suggested for integration were:

- Term Deals: the vocabulary of investment contracts
- Financing instruments: loans, invoice discounting, convertibles
- When to proceed with own resources (bootstrapping, family and friends) and when to look for investors?
- Platforms: what they are and how to build a product offer
- Choice of user features/experiences in PoC/MVPs: how to plan a product/service roadmap
- Measuring engagement/attraction: the Awareness-Action-Revenue-Recurrence-Referral (AARRR) funnel
- How to create a scalable and repeatable sales process and how to create a sales network.

within the **CC1.4 Fundraising task and subtasks**

- **Development of the Fundraising Network and Management:** according to their work plan, Spoke 8 (UniTS, PAA) members identified, through a call for experts, the providers for the organisation of a series of events and 1:1 activities for the accelerated teams.
- **Implementation of the VC-Invited Stage:** as of July 2025 the implementation has started, with a cycle of trainings and meetings with banking actors, business angels and structured investors. The initiatives are being offered in parallel for startups of the 1st and 2nd Acceleration round and each team is going to be contacted by one of the selected providers for a tailored 1:1 consultancy.

The "Vocabulary of credit" training sessions were completed and the recordings were provided to the startups, including topics such as:

- Personal Financial Management and Startup Readiness,
- Financial Risks and Personal Strategy,
- Italian Economic Context and Implications for Startups,
- Financing instruments for startups,
- Angel Investors
- Venture Capital
- Crowdfunding
- Public Funding
- Non-Repayable Grants
- Reporting
- How banks evaluate individuals

- Bank financial instruments
- Financial sustainability analysis
- Debt guarantees
- Financing long-term investments
- Safe access to credit
- Protection tools and support
- Key parameters for credit offers
- How and where to invest money
- Choosing financial intermediaries
- Key questions before making an investment
- Tools for evaluating offers

The “meetings with banks” sessions were also completed, including both in-person and online training sessions and the opportunity for startups to have 1 to 1 meeting with credit institutions of North eastern Italy.

The implementation of the “meetings with enterprises” initiative, fostering direct interaction with potential industry partners, is underway and will give startups the possibility to present their ideas through structured "speed-dating" activities.

The configuration of a modular web-app platform by an external provider is ongoing and it is expected to deliver a “High Potential Showroom and Venture Capitalist Platform” with a profiling tool and the following two main modules:

- a) Innovation matching consultancy (Presentation forms, Public dashboard with startup/spinoff showcase, Book a pitch and assess your skills)
- b) Development and Training (Specialized forms for consulting with VC funds or business angels, Training area, Networking area, Pitch verification).

For the “Consultations with a Venture Capitalist” initiative, the consulting firm has already delivered one-to-one coaching sessions to the first-cycle start-ups, assessing their projects and providing individual feedback. Meetings with the second-cycle start-ups began right after the end of the acceleration phase (demo day held in Venice on 26 June 2025) and are ongoing. The service will lead to the selection of 5 “ready to scale-up” startups eligible to access the next phase that will offer them:

- a customized support program to define optimal fundraising strategies
- identification of three investment funds/VC operators potentially interested in each project, with support in adapting the business plan, including the financial plan and pre-money valuation, to meet their requirements
- organization of two individual meetings per start-up with potential investors and companies.

The organisation of the “Final event” is ongoing: it will be held on 18 September 2025 in Trieste and will serve as a showcase for the innovation ecosystem. One of the appointed consulting companies is collaborating with UNITS to identify and engage investors to be invited to the event. In addition, it will ensure the on-site presence of its representatives to facilitate direct communication between start-ups and investors and to support the teams in effectively presenting their projects to attract potential funding.

- **Design of the Sustainable Stage:** a “Legal sanity check” desk/service (on request) has been activated by UniPD. An additional investor contact activity has been planned by UniPD to reinforce this SubTask. A final event has also been planned for the 18th of September 2025 and will take place in Trieste (Urban Center), involving various stakeholders, including potential investors, some of the Open Innovation companies, representatives from the North-East territories and representatives from the 9 partner Universities.

General **outcomes** from the cross cutting perspective are:

- the good practices in dialogue settings among different Spokes, with the related common procedures and tools that have been designed, implemented and fine-tuned in Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration and Fundraising activities
- the mapping and targeted engagement of innovative companies in Northeast Italy to match their innovation trajectories with the CCI startup projects
- the development of a unified dialogue interface between CCI initiatives and quadruple helix actors.

ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS

Then, for the **encountered problems and (→) related corrective actions** in the cross cutting perspective, some reflections could be proposed:

- difficulties in defining criteria and indicators for the Open Innovation research action
→ collaboration of UniUD with UniTN, guided by the PL, successfully leading to the work methodology refinement and to the selection of a list of innovation oriented companies, divided into clusters
- criticalities of the 1st Acc. program structure and outcomes
→ methodological curvature of the Acceleration framework, functional in giving more structure to the startups (equally enhancing the communication part - pitch - with the documentation part for each of the elements underlying a business plan/strategic plan, starting with the development from POC to MVP)
 - more hands-on way of conducting workshops (45min “lecture” + work with N coaches on the field)
 - more workshops with introduction of an induced selection principle
 - implementation of software to support the Acc. phase, to give structure and continuity
 - intensification of coaching
- criticalities of the 2nd Acc. program structure and outcomes:
 - the teams were often incomplete and more time would be required to deepen and transfer economic and managerial competencies → potential integration of external members into the teams
 - teams generally struggled to clearly define the financial aspects (except for the more mature and experienced teams) → reinforcing and giving more space to workshops n. 4, 6 and 7 (Governance, mission & vision, strategy, business model; tools for AI; Action plan & Eco-Fin Plan; Eco-Fin Plan & funding)
 - team progress and performance monitoring was difficult and the evaluation system was not able to provide an easily understandable picture of the projects' status. nor to allow teams to conduct a self-assessment → improving the evaluation system (for example taking into consideration well-established frameworks such as the [KTH Innovation Readiness Level™](#) framework), reviewing also the role and degree of involvement of the external juries

- the “expert/senior coach” role was sometimes misinterpreted by the teams, requiring his/her help on highly sector-specific issues → activating on-demand consultants (not involved in the whole acceleration program) on verticals
- heterogeneity of the startups involved in the 2nd Acc. round (in terms of background, themes, but also maturity) → characterisation of the portfolio (mix between TRL and BRL plausible for the market, for the success of the Acc. and subsequent phases or Fundraising)
- delays in the implementation of the Fundraising phase → the Program Leader and Manager stimulated the Task leader towards the concretisation of the proposed work plan (combining the offer for the two “cohorts” of accelerated startups), while also outlining a backup action (based on networking) directly led by the CCI management team
- low live participation of the accelerated startups in the introductory fundraising sessions and in the one-on-one meetings with the consulting firm → all sessions were recorded and made accessible for asynchronous consultation + the consulting firm made targeted efforts to re-engage the less active participants
- difficulty in connecting with specific investors targeted on science-based, pre-seed / early stage initiatives → tailored activities foreseen for a reduced number of startups with the highest potential for attracting investments and scaling-up.

NEXT STEPS

Next steps to be met in the cross-cutting perspective are:

- Open Innovation: completing interviews with companies and analysing data to intersect their open innovation issues with the development trajectories of startups.
- Fundraising: completing the implementation of the phase (offering tailored support in dialoguing with enterprises and investors + legal support) with coordinated action of Spoke 5 and Spoke 8. The aim is to help all the accelerating startups in finding their optimal funding strategies, supporting the early stage startups in getting familiar with terminology and dynamics for startup funding. For the most promising, investment-ready startups the more ambitious goal is to assist them in developing a fundraising network, identifying and approaching potential investors including VC/BA and helping in negotiating/structuring investment deals, in their way to scaling-up.
 In parallel, in collaboration with Spoke 1, giving to a subset of the 2nd cycle accelerated startups an additional opportunity to present their project to relevant stakeholders of the Italian startup ecosystem during Bolzano Slush'd 2025 (3-4 September 2025).
- Data elaboration: completing the analysis of the effectiveness of the CCI program, in particular elaborating considerations on the completed Tasks (Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration) and extracting insights and recommendations for improvement.

References for the cross cutting perspective are in the common shared [Drive](#) environment, in the [CCI webpage](#) and inside the [Accelerator App CCI environment](#).

1. SPOKE 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Creating a startup is an exhilarating and daunting venture that requires thorough planning, strategic decision-making, and relentless determination. In today's fast-paced and highly competitive business landscape, it is crucial for aspiring entrepreneurs to engage in various activities that can pave the way for a successful startup. To achieve it, the Free University of Bolzano (unibz) has worked locally by extending his team with external personnel and implementing a call to find business ideas among his members; and at the consortium level by supporting the acceleration phase with various activities. Precisely, the process to hire three experts on supporting structure, development and their introduction to the markets have been identified and the hiring process has started. The three experts will be fully operational in the last part of the project. Moreover, in February 2025 the university council has approved the first "[unibz call 4 startup](#)". The call had a lot of interest, 18 ideas were submitted, 10 of them were selected to support a pre-acceleration phase. Unibz has also host one the acceleration meeting in May 9-10. The topic was action plan and econ-financial plan. Finally, unibz has started a series of meet-ups to increase interest of the academic environment to the start-up business. The first two events, on motivation and type of/support to start-ups have been scheduled on [May 8](#) and on [May 22](#).

1.1. SPOKE 1 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Title: Ecosystems for mountain innovation.

The Free University of Bolzano leads the activities of the Spoke 1 "Ecosystems for mountain innovation" and develops research and technology transfer activities in the interdisciplinary area of mountain ecosystems. The main general objective is encouraging the development of new products, processes, and lifestyles capable of consolidating or supporting local traditions that guarantee the survival and demographic vitality of the mountain contexts from any standpoints (economic, environmental and social).

In the CC1 activity, the first objective of unibz has been to create a team of specialist and startup analysts. The work in early 2025 has been to enlarge the composition of the team with internal and external figures. The team will be fully operational for the second part of 2025.

The second objective of unibz has been to promote the pre-acceleration and acceleration phases. We organized a new internal call for startups in winter 2025. 18 ideas were submitted, 10 of them were selected and currently support in a pre-acceleration phase.

1.2. SPOKE 1 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

To disseminate its activities, the Free University of Bolzano has undertaken two primary initiatives. In February 2025 a new "[unibz call 4 startup](#)" has been promoted. The call had a lot of interest, 18 ideas were submitted, 10 of them were selected to support a pre-acceleration phase.

Second, unibz has started a series of meet-ups to increase interest of the academic environment to the start-up business. The first event with title "Entrepreneurs and start-ups" was on May 8 and it provided a platform for exploration of the theoretical frameworks underpinning successful start-ups, a successful business experience and team activities to promote collaborations. Active participation was encouraged and a stimulating exchange of ideas among students, faculty, and researchers was started. The second event with title "Types of company, their structure and possible support" was on May 22. This meet-up focused on start-up companies, their financing and support. The typical financial structure of startups funded by venture capitals and, even earlier, by business angels was presented, illustrating the contractual clauses usually employed to manage the various conflicts of

interest between founders and funders in this regard. Then, EIT Digital, a key pillar of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), was introduced and cases on how startups can benefit from one of Europe's largest and most dynamic digital innovation ecosystems will be shown.

1.3. SPOKE 1 CCI MAIN RESULTS

The Free University of Bolzano has created a group of five professors and two external members with specialization on ideation and market research to assessing funding options; producing business plans; and delivering new products to the market. The group has studied the best contract possible for hiring experts with relevant experience and motivation on creating and developing startups resulting in an appalto.

The team has also worked on the promotion of the pre-acceleration and acceleration activities. For the pre-acceleration phase, an unibz call for startups has been implemented from February 2025. A series of meet-ups have also started. For the acceleration phase, unibz has hosted an event on May 9-10. The sessions focused on refining market entry strategies, delineating clear milestones for product development, and establishing scalable operational frameworks. A significant portion of the meeting was dedicated to reviewing financial projections, including detailed funding requirements, revenue models, and burn rate analyses, ensuring alignment with realistic market expectations and investor confidence. The resulting action plan incorporates agile methodologies for implementation, coupled with rigorous financial monitoring protocols designed to support sustainable growth and mitigate early-stage risks.

1.4. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

Defining the optimal contract for all activities has proven challenging even this year.

Firstly, regarding personnel, the standard post-doctoral position (assegni di ricerca) has been too restrictive to attract candidates with experience in startup project analysis. This may be due to a scarcity of individuals with such combined expertise and local competition from the NOI Techpark incubator. To address this, an "appalto" contract was utilized.

Secondly, for activities with externals, we encountered concerns that participation and sponsorship could be perceived as arbitrarily transferring of public funds to a private entity. Again, the "appalto" contract was employed as a solution. However, it's important to note that using the "appalto" model imposes a significant administrative burden on the institution and all involved parties.

In summary, unibz has faced considerable difficulties in transferring public funds to private partners while maintaining objectivity and impartiality. While the implemented solutions are robust in addressing these challenges, they are admittedly inefficient.

1.5. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The next steps for the 2025 activities relate to completing the hiring of analysts who possess advanced skills in startup composition, structure and future development. Moreover, unibz will support the participation of iNEST to [Bolzano slush'd 2025](#). Finally, we will continue the meet-ups initiative.

For the future, unibz is exploring the possibility of implementing a permanent program after the INEST project concludes. The three main challenges are: 1) establishing a network of motivated stakeholders; 2) identifying appropriate solutions in collaboration with partners; and 3) securing funding.

References

PNRR-iNEST Project and Start-ups (2204/09/02) "The New Role of Triveneto Universities in the Creation of Innovative Enterprises", NOI Techpark Auditorium A2.2.32, Bolzano.

2. SPOKE 2 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Spoke 2 activities focus on applied research and technology transfer related to the areas of health, wellness and healthy eating. These thematic areas are declined in the Spoke in a broad sense, including the related enabling infrastructures, both physical and digital, and the digital transformation of companies and entities operating in the related supply chains.

The Spoke's main mission is to enhance technological development and social innovation to promote the health and well-being of citizens and support the digital and green transition of the Triveneto social and health system. The Spoke will pursue this ambitious goal by combining the study, development, and testing of enabling sciences and technologies in various fields: from artificial intelligence to digital health, biotechnology, omics, electronics, and robotics. The project will not only deal with technology, but will properly take into consideration the relevant social, historical, economic and psychological context. The technologies developed will be integrated to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system in the Northeast, promoting innovative cures and treatments that can contribute to a healthy lifestyle and monitoring their impact on citizens and their quality of life.

Within the context of a citizen- and patient-centered framework, the objective of Spoke 2 is to foster technical and social innovation with the purpose of enhancing human health and well-being, as well as providing assistance to the transition of Triveneto health systems to digital and environmentally friendly practices. The ambitious overarching aim will be pursued by Spoke 2 by the utilization of enabling technologies and sciences, which include Artificial Intelligence, Digital Health, Biotechnology, Omic Technologies, Electronics, and Robotics. This will be done within the framework of social, historical, economic, and psychological factors. In order to contribute to the digital transformation of the socio-economic system of the Triveneto region, technologies will be incorporated. This will involve the promotion of innovative treatments and therapies for a healthy lifestyle, as well as the monitoring of the influence these technologies have on inhabitants and the quality of life they experience.

Within more specific reference to the Cross Cutting activity 1 – Support the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs, the Spoke 2 promotes itself as a catalyst inside the university system to foster the creation of startups initiatives with business ideas related to health, food, and lifestyle. The is an important player in the context of innovation ecosystems, offering access to advanced research resources and aiding the incubation of breakthrough ideas.

The goal is to create real impacts in the form of new processes, products, and services that will strengthen the iNEST Ecosystem. The projects produced focus not just on issues of research and technology innovation, but also on assisting emerging businesses in developing innovation strategies. Spoke 2 strongly encourages the use of digital tools and technology in this context, including them into both research and development efforts and the new goods and services that come from them. This combination between academic research and entrepreneurial spirit within the institution generates a dynamic ecosystem that fosters the development and growth of new firms, contributing considerably to the innovation landscape.

2.1. SPOKE 2 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

(title of the task, brief description of the topics, participants, general organisation and planning, expected results)

Title: Cross-cutting Activity: Support the Generation and Development of Research Start-ups and Spin-offs [CC1] for the **Spoke 2:** Health, Food and Lifestyle

Research Topics: RT1 – Digital Health and Systems for the Citizens; RT2 – Biotechnologies and Pharmaceutical Technologies; RT3 – Devices for Health; RT4 – Food and Health

Participants: Prof. Alessandro Rossi (Spoke 2 CC1 Principal Investigator and Rector's Delegate on Business Support); Prof. Sandro Trento (School of Innovation - SOI Director); Prof. Erica Santini (Department of Economics and Management, Delegate for Internationalization); Prof. Andrea Caputo (Department of Economics and Management, Director of the Master in International Management)).

General Organization and Planning: At the University of Trento, key activities within Spoke 2: Health, Food, and Lifestyle will be a strategic mix of scouting and acceleration activities, aligned with the overarching design of an innovation ecosystem that supports the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs. This approach is characterized by a dual structure:

Firstly, the Pre-Acceleration phase will be managed in a decentralized yet coordinated manner across all SPOKES. This structure is essential for generating and selecting innovative ideas that can evolve into research start-ups and spin-offs. The decentralized aspect of this phase allows for direct support to emerging entrepreneurs, including students, PhD candidates, and researchers. Simultaneously, coordination across SPOKES ensures the replication of economies, the development of methodologies, and the creation of technological platforms that are applicable to all SPOKES, drawing from the best cases at each university.

Secondly, the Acceleration & Fundraising phases will be centrally managed. This phase is crucial for defining the business model of the research start-ups and spin-offs and managing investment rounds to facilitate market entry and scaling. Centralized management during these phases allows for economies of scale, utilizing methodologies and technological platforms that have been developed and tested.

At the University of Trento, the contribution to these phases will be twofold: local scouting activities will be carried out via a scouting specialist who will focus on identifying and nurturing promising ideas within the university. Additionally, the centralized acceleration activities will be supported through startup analysis, ensuring that the transition from idea to market is as smooth and efficient as possible, thereby enhancing the potential for successful market entry and growth of these ventures.

Also, the local research group will engage in regular meetings to coordinate efforts and ensure alignment of objectives. Additionally, regular interactions are planned with ecosystem stakeholders, including HIT and Trentino Sviluppo, as well as with other iNEST CC1 research units. This collaborative approach is designed to harness diverse expertise and resources for effective innovation and entrepreneurial growth.

Expected Results: The expected results include the successful establishment of an operational framework for innovation, the development of a skilled and informed pool of innovators through the execution of various awareness and pre-acceleration programs, and the effective identification and nurturing of potential startups and spin-offs in the subsequent acceleration and funding stages. This collective effort aims to result in tangible advancements in the research and development of health, food, and lifestyle-related technologies and solutions.

2.2. SPOKE 2 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "2"

Background: a series of initiatives at Unitrento are concerned with raising awareness on innovation and entrepreneurship among students and scholars. Central to these efforts is the School of Innovation (SOI), which offers interdisciplinary training blending technical, scientific, and humanistic approaches to innovation. The SOI's curriculum, enriched by the Crash Course in Intellectual Property Rights, equips participants with essential knowledge for ideating, validating and protecting innovation. Also, through initiatives like the Business Design program and the Start-Up Lab, participants gain practical skills in market analysis, business strategy, and human-centered design, laying a strong foundation for entrepreneurial ventures. The Proof of Concept (POC) program is reserved for patent holders and supports the efforts towards translating theoretical knowledge into viable, market-ready initiatives. The newly created Springboard of Startups program allows students to engage with stakeholders and successful founders, both raising awareness on entrepreneurship and fostering the next generation of innovators. The Open Office allows students and researchers to book one of four weekly 45-minutes slots to receive tailored support and entrepreneurial counseling. Starting from 2025, existing entrepreneurial-adjacent initiatives such as the "100 progetti per il Comune di Trento" of the Department of Information Sciences and Engineering are now presided by

the SOI, and exploitable projects are awarded with tailored support to increase the University spinoff output. Collaboration with Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) further strengthens the university's capacity in technology transfer and innovation, bridging academic research with market opportunities through the participation in the Trentino Startup Valley program. These programs collectively act as a springboard for scouting and pre-acceleration activities, preparing participants not just in ideation but also in the practical aspects of launching and scaling innovative solutions in the competitive market of health and wellness.

State of the art: The theoretical and practical basis of Trento University's entrepreneurship and innovation activities are founded on a wide range of scholarly works and practice-based theories. This includes, but is not limited to, key contributions such as Lombardi and Berk's thoughts on "Startup Program Design," which provide useful frameworks for organizing entrepreneurial acceleration and incubation programs. Eric Ries' 'The Lean Startup' is another good example, demonstrating the importance of constant innovation in the entrepreneurial process. Additionally, among other resources, Steve Blank's 'The Four Steps to the Epiphany' and 'The Startup Owner's Manual,' co-authored with Bob Dorf, serve as significant tools, providing extensive strategies for starting and maintaining successful companies. In practical terms, in the above-mentioned programs and initiatives, the university incorporates approaches such as design thinking, which encourages creative problem-solving and user-centered product development. The lean startup methodology and its validation concepts are critical in fostering a culture of quick prototyping and iterative testing, which is required for rapidly validating business ideas. Based on these beliefs, business modeling assists participants in developing viable business models, whereas effective thinking promotes an adaptive, resource-oriented approach to entrepreneurship. This combination of academic knowledge and practical approaches fosters innovation by leading participants from the early phases of idea development to the difficulties of establishing and scaling a start-up.

Methodology: The scouting methodology employed in the Spoke 2 for identifying and nurturing entrepreneurial opportunities is a strategic mix of pull and push approaches. Actively hunting for ideas, the university engages in detailed interviews with researchers, conducts comprehensive mapping of research group efforts, and undertakes desk analysis of its existing portfolio of academic startups and patents. This proactive push approach is complemented by a pull strategy, where the university orchestrates various awareness and capacity-building activities such as courses, workshops, and seminars aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset. Additionally, initiatives like open office hours and open call programs are implemented to encourage the spontaneous emergence of new ideas and ventures. This dual-method approach ensures a thorough and dynamic process of scouting, effectively tapping into both existing and latent entrepreneurial potential within the university community. Lastly, best practices in automated AI-based scouting and spinoff development are benchmarked.

Ongoing activities: To find and support innovation inside its ecosystem, Spoke 2 at the University of Trento has started a thorough series of scouting efforts. In order to provide a continuous perspective of the inventive outputs that are already available as well as possible areas for future development, these operations started with the careful mapping of patents and other Intellectual Resources (IRs). Concurrently, the university began a comprehensive mapping of research groups and main investigators with the goal of identifying both innovation hotspots and strategic research areas where the IP output and valorisation could be improved. This propaedeutic activity enables a tailored approach to foster existing entrepreneurial drivers and to stimulate the emergence of such drivers in underrepresented areas of competence. The university's methods are continually checked to make sure they remain in line with worldwide standards of excellence through this process, which involves

benchmarking against national and international best practices. In addition to these strategic objectives, the research group is conducting a detailed literature assessment and stakeholder interviews on scouting tactics to improve and develop its methodology. European and Italian excellence centres for academic entrepreneurship are mapped, thoroughly analysed, and whenever possible interviewed (usually in the persons of TTOs representatives). Based on these analyses, key areas for improvement in best practices are identified and an improvement strategy is outlined. In parallel, entrepreneurial projects that are not accredited as academic spinoffs (i.e. prospective academic spinoffs and existing enterprises that did not undergo the accreditation process) are interviewed to understand key unmet needs and/or deterrent factors in the accreditation process. Consequently, the current regulation for accreditation of university spinoffs is being reviewed supporting the UniTN TTO personnel. Spoke 2 has initiated a number of programs to increase awareness and develop capacity for entrepreneurial engagement in tandem with these strategic goals. These consist of the Springboard of Startups (SOS) Program, the Business Design Program, the Business Growth Program, the Crash Course on Intellectual Property Rights, and the Open Office. As additional support to students and research teams, the School of Innovation (SOI), which is actively attempting to cultivate an innovative and entrepreneurial culture among students and researchers, offers a comprehensive 12 ECTS curriculum in line with these goals.

Lastly, a number of AI-based tools are being tested for integration in the current scouting workflow and business design and validation support activities. These include both commercially available and open-source tools, as well as custom tools that are being created in-house.

2.3. SPOKE 2 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

(e.g., conferences, meetings, participation in kick-off and mid-term plenary sessions, overall working group activities, interaction with the stakeholders)

The University of Trento is playing an active role in shaping the post-iNEST strategy through the design of the venture builder “iNEST2impact”, which will build on the achievements of the consortium to further sustain the creation and growth of research-based startups. In parallel, UniTrento is collaborating with Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) and Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) on the development of a joint Proof of Concept program, aimed at reinforcing shared approaches to research valorisation and technology transfer across the regional innovation ecosystem.

In 2025, the School of Innovation contributed to UniCredit’s “Imprenditori #GenNext” initiative with the design and delivery of a three-day entrepreneurship masterclass for prospective graduates. The success of this first edition has already led to SOI’s involvement in planning the 2026 programme. In addition, SOI is coordinating a joint winter school in entrepreneurship with the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, to be held in December 2025, where mixed teams of researchers and students will work on the market valorization of ideas coming from research teams.

Finally, UniTrento has recently consolidated its partnership with the European Space Agency’s Business Incubation Centre in Padova. Through this collaboration, the School of Innovation supports scouting activities aimed at identifying, mentoring and valorising space-related research outcomes from UniTrento, ensuring that scientific results are effectively channelled towards entrepreneurial opportunities.

2.4. SPOKE 2 CCI MAIN RESULTS

(main results achieved till now, including pictures, photos, graphs, table, link to on-line material, etc...)

As far as the participation of Spoke 2 teams in the acceleration stage is concerned, three out of the four startup ideas successfully completed the acceleration program. Additionally, three startup ideas that were not accepted into the acceleration stage are currently being mentored by the scouting specialist and the startup analyst. Among these, two have applied and were admitted to the regional acceleration program (Trentino Startup Valley) coordinated by Trentino Sviluppo with Fondazione Hub Innovazione Trentino.

To further enhance coordination within the innovation ecosystem, a number of meetings have been organised with Hub Innovazione Trentino, Trentino Sviluppo, and Fondazione Bruno Kessler. These meetings have improved alignment between the various stakeholders and led to the scheduling of a conjoined Proof of Concept (PoC) program between FBK and the University of Trento, aimed at improving the business readiness level of promising research-based technologies and innovations.

The "Springboard of Startups" program concluded its first academic year with a total of 12 events, including founder talks, panels with innovation stakeholders, and pitching sessions of prospective student spinoffs. The initiative has now fostered a growing community of 135 individuals interested in entrepreneurship, ranging from early-stage student innovators to experienced academic researchers.

The "Open Office" initiative was also launched as an ongoing, low-barrier access point for entrepreneurial dialogue within the academic and research community. This initiative led to the identification of a number of new entrepreneurial projects involving students, researchers, and professors. The selected projects span a broad spectrum of development stages—from early ideation to prototype validation—and present varying levels of patentability, technological and business readiness, and market exploitability.

As a result of the accelerator's Call for Ideas, of the Springboard of Startups program, and of the Open Office initiative, a total of 20 business projects, from startup ideas to incorporated companies, are being followed with tailored support strategies by the scouting specialist and the startup analyst.

2.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

No new relevant problems arose during 2024, with the corrective actions outlined in the report of January 2024 having succeeded in solving the identified issues. Therefore, the delays accumulated during 2024 have been successfully recovered.

2.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2025 activities)

Moving forward, the actions of the Spoke 2 will focus on:

Design of a curricular entrepreneurship program for student entrepreneurs. Building on the experience of the extracurricular Springboard of Startups, a new elective curricular program is being designed to systematically identify and engage students with entrepreneurial potential. The program will offer structured training and mentorship and will focus on matching students with high-potential, exploitable research outputs generated within the university and partner research centers. The goal is to facilitate the creation of multidisciplinary teams and guide them through a structured opportunity validation process, from problem-solution fit to early business modeling. The program will also serve as a funnel for scouting promising startup ideas, connecting them early with the resources and actors of the local innovation ecosystem. The integration of this program into the academic curriculum is

expected to increase the volume and quality of early-stage ventures originating from within the university, and provides a competitive edge in the educational offer of the University.

Launch of a joint Proof of Concept program between UniTN and FBK. Following a series of coordination meetings among the University of Trento, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, and other regional stakeholders, a joint Proof of Concept (PoC) program is being developed to accelerate the market-readiness of research-based innovations. The program will focus on funding and supporting the validation of the technological, commercial, and societal impact of selected research results through tailored mentorship, prototyping resources, and early customer engagement. The PoC initiative is designed to align internal procedures and criteria for project selection across institutions, promoting a more efficient and collaborative approach to technology transfer. By addressing the gap between research and innovation, this initiative is expected to strengthen the pipeline of ventures and spin-offs emerging from both institutions.

Continuous contribution to the design of the iNEST2IMPACT Venture Studio. Throughout the project, UniTN participated in a series of monthly meetings in Venice to set the agenda and design the venture studio to be established in follow-up to the iNEST project. UniTN shall give its continuative contribution to this endeavour. UniTN already benchmarked the best-performing entrepreneurial universities as well as academic, public and private venture builders and venture studios, engaging the most virtuous in conversations to share knowledge and best practices. Furthermore, UniTN will continuously update the consortium on the proceedings of its pilot programs, which can provide foundational knowledge to better design the venture studio. Key efforts in capacity building are currently being made at UniTN, especially in integrating AI tools in the K&T valorisation workflow, and and overcoming the current limitations of literature databases—an essential prerequisite for their effective use. UniTN shall retrospectively report to the consortium the output of such efforts, which will remove potential operational bottlenecks for the studio. Dedicated scouting specialists will play a key role in identifying and nurturing high-potential projects, ultimately increasing the rate of transformation from research to funded spin-offs and fostering innovation with tangible societal impact.

Optimisation and harmonisation of educational and awareness programs. To broaden the pool of prospective founders, both the newly created Springboard of Startups (SoS) will be further tailored to the needs of the engaged students and researchers. A steering committee composed of the Startup Analyst, the Scouting Specialist, a SOI professor, and three students/researchers has been created. This committee will re-adjust the program offer based on the feedback collected *in itinere*. Furthermore, SoS will be better harmonised to the educational offer at the School of Innovation, in order to support and empower existing programs and courses. This is expected to: a) reach talented individuals at the very early career stage, b) increase the number of perspective founders, and c) increase the university's output in terms of startup ideas and academic spinoffs.

Harmonisation of initiatives with HIT and TS. While the Trentino ecosystem is already well established, with several public agencies dedicated to supporting startups and developing the local economy, this sometimes is a source of confusion for academic founders. This is due to the pathway for commercial exploitation of IP, from the incorporation to the acceleration, and which agencies should be involved at which stage, being very clear to the stakeholders but overwhelming for prospective founders. The effort of co-designing such pathways and effectively communicating it to students and researchers is currently undergoing. This is expected to add clarity and facilitate and encourage founders in taking the entrepreneurial initiative. In parallel, this is also bound to harmonise KPIs across different stakeholders, further streamlining the process of supporting the emergence of innovative startups. **Revision of the University's spinoff regulation.** The scouting process highlighted a number of entrepreneurial projects, some of which already incorporated and incubated/accelerated,

that are generated within the University but are not accredited as academic spinoffs. The proponents of such projects, as well as prospective founders, are being interviewed to understand barriers and resistances that are deterring them from applying to the accreditation. In parallel, a benchmarking analysis is being performed to identify the best practices in Italian and European entrepreneurial universities. With the support of the university's TTO, these inputs are being used to review and identify key improvement areas in the university spinoff regulation. The improvement of the best practices in terms of support/benefits given to academic spinoffs is expected to increase the Spoke 2 output in terms of officially accredited spinoffs.

Exploration and piloting of new processes and tools. The Startup Analyst and Scouting Specialist have been dedicated in benchmarking best practices across Italian and European entrepreneurial universities. These include processes for venture creation and AI-based tools for integration in the current scouting workflow and business design and validation support activities. Specifically, the possibility of establishing an academic venture builder exploiting the university's pool of talents and knowledge is currently being explored. Supporting these efforts, a number of AI tools that are currently being used in TTOs of European entrepreneurial universities are currently being tested and selected for integration into the established scouting process.

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3. SPOKE 3 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

Coordinated by the University of Udine, Spoke 3's research efforts are dedicated to driving innovation and supporting the green and digital transformation of the advanced manufacturing sector. These research activities are organized into five thematic areas, or research topics (RTs)

- 1 RT1: Energy
- 2 RT2: Smart manufacturing, Mechatronics and Robotics
- 3 RT3: Materials
- 4 RT4: Artificial Intelligence and Data Science
- 5 RT5: Organizational, economical and legal aspects

Within the iNEST project, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 (CC1) plays a key role in fostering a coordinated and integrated strategy across all Spokes. Functioning within an innovation ecosystem framework, it seeks to maximize the impact of innovative ideas, supporting the creation and development of science-based startups and spin-offs.

3.1. SPOKE 3 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

As previously noted, the primary aim of CC1 is to support the creation and growth of science-based startups and spin-offs emerging from the academic community. This objective defines the entire cross-cutting activity and is shared across all Spokes, regardless of the specific research themes associated to each university.

3.2. SPOKE 3 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development

of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.

Responsible: UNIUD

Duration: months 9-40

- **CC1.3: Acceleration**

- Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 11-34

- Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 14-40

- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, sprint program and Demo Day. The objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 3

Background / State of the Art: Some of the activities related to Scouting and Pre-acceleration phase have been concluded after the Selection Day of the second cycle, which was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024. Nevertheless, during the reporting period, Spoke 3's working group continued to support the main goal of CC1, proposing activities aimed at engaging the academic community on startup and entrepreneurship topics.

Methodology: During the reporting period, Spoke 3 consolidated what had been done during the second cycle of the Scouting and Pre-acceleration phases. In this perspective, another edition of the initiative "Start Cup Udine" was organized. Like the previous one, it consisted of a series of events, workshops and training sessions concerning entrepreneurship and startup fundamentals. The initiative was structured as follows:

- Phase 1: From idea to startup

- Business Idea Analysis
- Business Idea SWOT Analysis
- Business Model Canvas
- Value Proposition and Market
- Legal forms of enterprises
- Opportunities and services to build on innovative ideas

- Phase 2: Pitch Preparation

- Business Plan fundamentals
- Intellectual Property

- o Economic and Financial Plan
- o Pitch Preparation

- Phase 3: Tailored Services for Business Plan Preparation

- o Mentoring program (10 hours)
- o Advise on economic and financial aspects (2 hours)
- o Logo design and realization

Phase 1 was targeted to all potential participants interested in entrepreneurship, namely students, researchers and professors with or without an idea and a team. For Phase 2, a defined team (at least two persons) and a brief abstract of the idea were required. At the end of this phase, teams were asked to prepare a pitch deck and to present it to the internal committee, formed by professors and startup professionals. The committee decided whether the teams could proceed to Phase 3, which – as described in the next paragraph – consists in a series of tailored consulting/advisory services.

Finally, during the reporting period Spoke 3, in collaboration with the Coordinator of CC1, carried out also some activities related to Sub Task CC1.2.4 “Open innovation”. In particular, some of the companies previously identified as the most innovative ones, were contacted and some of them were interviewed, in order to qualitatively assess how they manage innovation. Specifically, Spoke 3 was involved in the interview of Thermokey SPA.

Ongoing activities: Current activities are related to Phase 3 of the initiative Start Cup Udine. Teams who successfully completed the first two phases will have the opportunity of being supported by experts and professionals in the preparation of the business plan of their entrepreneurial project. In particular, they will have access to a 10 hours mentoring program, and to a 2 hours consultancy on financial aspects with an accountant. Moreover, a marketing and communication agency will design and realize a logo for each project.

Focus on Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities.

Development of a Methodology for Recruiting Innovation-Oriented Companies

During the reporting period, the methodology for recruiting innovation-oriented companies to be involved in Open Innovation activities was revised several times. Together with the Coordinator of CC1, a final decision was made to adopt a methodology divided into two phases. Each phase required the use of specific indicators to assess the companies’ innovation performance, which were selected based on a review of the scientific literature on corporate innovation analysis and measurement.

In Phase 1, all corporations based in North-East Italy were analyzed, without size constraints (285,422 companies), using indicators derived from financial statement data. The data source used was the AIDA database (Bureau Van Dijk – Moody’s Analytics), which enabled both aggregate and individual access and analysis of the financial statements filed with the Chambers of Commerce. The output was a preliminary ranking of companies in North-East Italy based on their innovation orientation.

In Phase 2, the top 350 companies with revenues exceeding €50 million were further analyzed using an expanded set of indicators, which included those from Phase 1 as well as additional indicators related to patents and participation in innovation and R&D projects.

After normalizing the indicator values, a new ranking of the 350 innovation-oriented companies was created. These companies were then grouped into thematic clusters based on Pavitt's taxonomy: Science-Based; Specialized Suppliers; Scale and Information Intensive; Supplier Dominated.

Open Innovation Day

At the conclusion of the analysis, mapping, and selection process of innovation-oriented companies, a public award event was organized to award the 38 most innovation-oriented companies, grouped according to Pavitt's thematic clusters. The event took place on Thursday, January 30, 2025, in the Aula Magna of Palazzo del Bo at the University of Padua. The organization was carried out in coordination with the Program Leader of Cross-Cutting Activity 1, the University of Padua (lead partner of the iNEST project), and the representatives of the iNEST Hub.

Below is the official event poster.

Open Innovation Day

Cross-Cutting Activity 1 – Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and spin-offs

<p>Ciovedì 30 gennaio 2025 dalle 16:30 alle 19:00</p>	<p>Università degli Studi di Padova Aula Magna – Palazzo del Bo Via VIII Febbraio 2, Padova</p>
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Il Consorzio iNEST riunisce nove tra Atenei e Istituti di Ricerca del Triveneto, insieme a numerosi Affiliati, con l'obiettivo di sviluppare tecnologie innovative per il benessere e la crescita economica e imprenditoriale nell'Italia del Nord-Est. Con l'**Open Innovation Day**, iNEST vuole favorire la collaborazione tra i centri di ricerca e le imprese, celebrando le eccellenze del territorio in termini di innovazione.

Programma		
16:30	Accoglienza e registrazione	17:30
17:00	Saluti istituzionali <i>Prof.ssa Daniela Mapelli – Rettrice dell'Università degli Studi di Padova</i> <i>Prof. Luciano Gamberini – Coordinatore Spoke 5 iNEST</i>	La mappatura delle imprese innovative del Nord-Est: criteri per la selezione <i>Prof. Piergiorgio Comuzzo – Referente dell'Università degli Studi di Udine per l'Attività Trasversale 1</i>
17:30	Il sistema dell'innovazione del Nord-Est: sfide e opportunità. Il progetto iNEST <i>Prof. Franco Bonollo – Presidente del Consorzio iNEST</i>	17:40
17:20	Le attività di Open Innovation del progetto iNEST <i>Prof. Carlo Bagnoli – Program Leader Attività Trasversale 1 iNEST</i>	Premiazione delle imprese più innovative del Nord-Est <i>Prof.ssa Patrizia Garengo – Università degli Studi di Padova</i>
		18:00
		Esperienze di Open Innovation a confronto (tavola rotonda) Moderano: <i>Prof. Carlo Bagnoli</i> <i>Prof.ssa Eleonora Di Maria – Referente dell'Università degli Studi di Padova per l'Attività Trasversale 1</i>

Registrazione L'evento è ad accesso libero, previa registrazione tramite il seguente modulo:
<https://forms.gle/yJHg2rcIGW8RCx5e7>

In preparation for the event, the following activities were carried out: definition of the event format (target audience, program, operational aspects); creation of a contact database for the selected companies (president, CEO, head of innovation); preparation of communication materials in coordination with SISSA; engagement of the awarded companies; creation of the award certificates.

Innovation-oriented company Interviews

To explore companies' innovation strategies and identify potential areas of collaboration, a series of structured interviews was conducted with previously selected innovation-oriented companies starting in February 2025.

To support these interviews, a standardized information sheet was prepared for each company, including general data, level of internationalization, information on the company's products and services, and areas of recent and future innovation. A total of 38 company profiles were completed, one for each company awarded during the event.

The interview questionnaire was developed by the Program Leader of Cross-Cutting Activity 1 and consists of open-ended questions aimed at understanding innovation strategies and potential synergies with the academic world. Thirty interviews were scheduled, including two with the participation of the iNEST Open Innovation Manager.

The coordination and implementation of these activities is currently overseen by the Program Leader of Cross-Cutting Activity 1.

Development of an Open Innovation Database

Starting in May 2025, a set of activities was launched—coordinated with the iNEST Hub—with the aim of testing and validating the methodology for identifying more innovation-oriented companies and building a structured database to support future Open Innovation initiatives.

The work included:

- defining relevant information categories to assess companies' previous experience in research-driven innovation and collaboration with universities;
- classifying companies according to the thematic spokes of iNEST, using a system based on the correspondence between ATECO codes and S3 macro-themes;
- testing the mapping, analysis, and selection methodology previously applied, by using it on a new sample of companies selected from the iNEST cascade calls;
- identifying a first set of companies with strong innovation potential that had not yet been actively involved in the project (e.g., non-funded applicants to the iNEST cascade calls and companies excluded from the TOP 100 in the previous ranking).

These activities are part of a broader effort to validate the methodology's consistency across different datasets and to lay the groundwork for a database of companies that can be involved in upcoming Open Innovation programs.

Support for the Organization of the iMATCH Initiative

Operational support was provided for the organization of *iMATCH*, an initiative promoted by the Alto Adriatico Technological Pole (an affiliated iNEST partner), in coordination with the iNEST Hub. The aim

is to connect iNEST researchers (with expiring contracts) with companies from North-East Italy seeking highly qualified profiles in research, development, and innovation.

The initiative includes three in-person events (*iMATCH Days*) to be held in Pordenone, Trento, and Vicenza, and makes use of the digital platform *Teamtaylor*, which was adapted to facilitate the matching process between companies and researchers.

The support activities included:

- technical and functional customization of the platform;
- assistance to companies with onboarding, job posting, and use of search tools;
- coordination support between the Technological Pole and iNEST university partners to ensure effective promotion of the event and engagement of researchers.

The events have been postponed to September 2025 to allow more preparation time and increase participation from both companies and researchers.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 3

Background / State of the Art: During the reporting period, the second cycle of the Acceleration program has been realized. Like the first one, the program was aimed at helping teams to develop their ideas from an entrepreneurial point of view and to prepare them to present their projects at the Demo Day, in front of an audience of potentially interested investors.

Methodology: The second cycle of the Acceleration program was similar to the first one. It consisted a series of workshops held in presence in some of the Universities of the consortium. Based on the lean startup methodology, the program covered all the fundamental concepts of entrepreneurship, allowing participants to gain some of the skills needed for developing their idea and running their future company.

The coaching scheme was maintained, even if it was slightly different from the previous cycle. Every startup was assigned two coaches: a senior one, with vertical experience in some specific field and a junior one, more focused on the operational point of view. The first one provided strategic advisory when needed, whereas the second supported teams on a daily basis in the development of the idea and in the realization of the deliverables required (namely Pitch Deck and Strategic Plan). As in the first cycle, the scouting specialist of Spoke 3 was involved in the program as a junior coach, supporting 3 startups of the cohort.

To summarize, the second cycle of the Acceleration program consisted in the following activities:

- *Workshop #1:* January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “*Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan*”.
- *Workshop #2:* February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “*Problem, current solutions, and Value proposition*”.
- *Workshop #3:* February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “*Market and competition*”.
- *Workshop #4:* March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca' Foscari): “*Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model*”.
- *Pitch Clinic #1:* April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav).
- *Workshop #5:* May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “*Action plan & eco-fin plan*”.
- *Workshop #6:* May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “*Eco-fin plan & funding*”.
- *Pitch Clinic #2:* June 6, 2025, in Verona.
- *Demo Day:* June 27, 2025, in Venice (Ca' Foscari)

3.3. SPOKE 3 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

During the reporting period, multiple coordination meetings were held, in order to promote effective communication and ensure correct alignment among the various teams participating in the project. In particular, every two weeks, all the coaches of the Acceleration program updated each other on the ongoing activities with the startups they were following in order to discuss common issues and find shared solutions.

As previously mentioned, one of the workshops of the Acceleration program was held in Udine, in the University farming facility, as described by the following posters.

Finanziato dall'Unione europea (NextGenerationEU) | Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca | Italiadomani | i NEST Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem

Mercato e Concorrenza

Programma di Accelerazione - Workshop 3

28 febbraio - 1 marzo 2025 14:00-18:30 e 9:00-13:00	Sale Rustici Azienda Agraria A. Servadei - sede di Udine S. Osvaldo Via Pozzuolo 324, Udine
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Modulo 1/2
Venerdì 28 febbraio
14:00-18:30

14:00-14:15	Introduzione e recap del lavoro fatto Presentazione da parte di 3 startup a scelta del lavoro svolto in autonomia e con i coach
14:15-15:00	Analisi del mercato (TAM-SAM-SOM) e dei segmenti di clientela prioritari <i>Alessandro Rossi</i>
15:00-16:00	Lavoro dei team con i coach sull'analisi di mercato e dei segmenti di clientela
16:00-16:15	Coffee break
16:15-17:45	Lavoro dei team con i coach sull'analisi di mercato e dei segmenti di clientela
17:45-18:15	Presentazione dell'analisi di mercato di 3 team e discussione

A seguire

20:30	Cena presso Ristorante Pizzeria Concordia (piazza 1 Maggio 9/A, Udine). Ristorante Pizzeria Concordia su Google Maps
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CC1 | uniba | UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO | UNIVERSITÀ TRIESTE | UNIVERSITÀ DI UDINE | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI TORINO | UNIVERSITÀ DI PADOVA | UNIVERSITÀ DI BARI AL FREDERICO II | UNIVERSITÀ DI BARI | UNIVERSITÀ DI BRESCIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI CAGLIARI | UNIVERSITÀ DI CATANIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI CANTÙ | UNIVERSITÀ DI CREMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI FERRARA | UNIVERSITÀ DI GENOVA | UNIVERSITÀ DI INDIRAGLIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI MILANO | UNIVERSITÀ DI MODENA E REGGIO EMILIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI NAPOLI | UNIVERSITÀ DI PALERMO | UNIVERSITÀ DI PARMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI PERUGIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI PISA | UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI TORINO | UNIVERSITÀ DI TRIESTE | UNIVERSITÀ DI TRENTO | UNIVERSITÀ DI VARESE | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA

Finanziato dall'Unione europea (NextGenerationEU) | Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca | Italiadomani | i NEST Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem

Mercato e Concorrenza

Programma di Accelerazione - Workshop 3

28 febbraio - 1 marzo 2025 14:00-18:30 e 9:00-13:00	Sale Rustici Azienda Agraria A. Servadei - sede di Udine S. Osvaldo Via Pozzuolo 324, Udine
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Modulo 2/2
Sabato 1 marzo
9:00-13:00

9:00-9:45	Analisi e studio della concorrenza diretta e indiretta <i>Alessandro Rossi</i>
9:45-10:30	Lavoro dei team con i coach sullo studio della concorrenza
10:30-10:45	Coffee break
10:45-12:15	Strumenti per il posizionamento competitivo - presentazione e lavoro dei team con i coach
12:15-12:45	Presentazione del posizionamento competitivo di 3 team e discussione
12:45-13:00	Recap e lavoro in vista del prossimo workshop

Info & Tips

Location
La sede dell'[Azienda Agraria A. Servadei](#) è raggiungibile dalla stazione di Udine con l'autobus n° 3, in circa 10 minuti. Chi arriva con i mezzi pubblici sarà accompagnato alle Sale Rustici.

Percheggi
Davanti all'azienda è disponibile un ampio parcheggio gratuito.

Pernottamento
Suggeriamo di alloggiare in centro (es. Astoria Hotel Italia) o eventualmente in zona stazione (es. Ambassador Palace Hotel).

CC1 | uniba | UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO | UNIVERSITÀ TRIESTE | UNIVERSITÀ DI UDINE | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI TORINO | UNIVERSITÀ DI PADOVA | UNIVERSITÀ DI BARI AL FREDERICO II | UNIVERSITÀ DI BARI | UNIVERSITÀ DI BRESCIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI CAGLIARI | UNIVERSITÀ DI CATANIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI CANTÙ | UNIVERSITÀ DI CREMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI FERRARA | UNIVERSITÀ DI GENOVA | UNIVERSITÀ DI INDIRAGLIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI MILANO | UNIVERSITÀ DI MODENA E REGGIO EMILIA | UNIVERSITÀ DI NAPOLI | UNIVERSITÀ DI PALERMO | UNIVERSITÀ DI PARMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI PISA | UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA | UNIVERSITÀ DI TORINO | UNIVERSITÀ DI TRIESTE | UNIVERSITÀ DI TRENTO | UNIVERSITÀ DI VARESE | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA | UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA

Moreover, in the scope of the initiative Start Cup Udine 2025, a public event was held in order to promote the initiative and to provide information about opportunities for startups and success stories, together with some relevant institutional partners, such as Invitalia, TEC4I FVG and Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico.

The corresponding poster can be found below.

STARTUPPER SPRITZ

Opportunità e servizi per sviluppare idee innovative

5 giugno 2025
ore 15.30

Aula multimediale SMACT3
UniuLab Village
Via Sondrio 2, Udine

Programma

SALUTI

Giovanni Cortella
Delegato al Trasferimento
Tecnologico dell'Università di Udine
e coordinatore Start Cup Udine

Piergiorgio Comuzzo
Referente dell'Università di Udine
per progetto INEST - Attività trasversale
CCI

Marco Sortino
Referente dell'Università di Udine
per progetto ACROSS - Task 3.4

INTERVENTI

*Servizi, strumenti e incentivi
per le idee d'impresa. Invitalia
a sostegno delle start up.*

Daniele De Angelis
Invitalia (collegamento da remoto)

*Da Start Cup a Start up
dell'Università:
il caso di FoodLife Next*

**Mariisa Alongi, Monica Anese,
Maria Cristina Nicoli,
Marika Valentino, Marco Lopriore**
FoodLife Next srl

*Da idee nel cassetto a casi
di successo. Il ruolo degli incubatori
per il sostegno alle start up.*

**Ilenia Grassato
TEC4IFVG
Elisa Fabbro**
Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico
"Andrea Galvani"

Startupper Spritz

Iscrizioni

<https://www.uniud.it/it/servizi/impres/punto-impresa/startcup-udine-2025/form-online-workshop>

3.4. SPOKE 3 CCI MAIN RESULTS

During the reporting period, both of the teams coming from Spoke 3 successfully completed the Acceleration Program and presented their project during the Demo Day.

With respect to the Start Cup initiative, 11 teams presented their project to the committee and all of them were admitted to Phase 3. As already mentioned, they will now have access to a series of tailored services.

3.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

One of the challenges faced during the research activities was represented by the relatively low engagement of the academic community in entrepreneurial initiatives. Traditional academic reward systems often prioritize research publications and scholarly impact, which can result in limited motivation for faculty and researchers to pursue entrepreneurship or the commercial application of their findings. Such endeavors are frequently not recognized as equally important in academic career progression.

3.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

(With reference to the 2025 activities)

In the following months, Spoke 3 will continue to pursue the primary goal of CC1, trying also to exploit and to leverage the traction and the results obtained so far during the project.

4. SPOKE 4 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

The main objective of Spoke 4 is to ally all the stakeholders participating in the built environment transformation to overcome the current challenges and adapt to social, economic and climate changes. Hence, the Spoke has the chance of becoming the node connecting all the sub-systems of the territorial transformation, promoting a collaborative and synergistic network between all the supply chain and sector operators: academic research, design practice, manufacturing, construction, commerce and distribution, the credit system, and public administrations.

- **RT1 - Strategic plan for the development of the construction and sustainable design sectors.** RT1 developed an analysis of the built environment while maintaining a transscale approach. RT1 identified the main sustainability objectives for the following building phase in Italy, the first to transform the built environment non-expansively;
- **RT2 - Technological solutions for the construction and sustainable design sectors,** RT2 identified an innovative method for selecting the survey areas according to the most sensitive territory for each topic and tested the technique in eleven different sites;
- **RT3 - Interaction between environments and human beings in the construction and sustainable design sectors.** In the first year, it aimed to identify the most critical issues regarding collective and individual well-being. The first year acted as a pivot in managing relations between general studies in the Northeast;

In this scientific context, **cross-cutting activity 1** is essential in fostering entrepreneurship education and dissemination within university ecosystems, connecting the business world with the scientific community to maintain a collaborative network over time.

One of the goals is to integrate research institutes to interact with the regional context, with the ultimate goal of contributing to creating a market economy through continuous trade and synergistic interactions.

4.1. SPOKE 4 CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 aims to foster the development and selection of innovative ideas arising from the scientific work of Spoke 4, with the ultimate goal of transforming them into research start-ups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CC1 is structured into four specific phases:

- **CC1.1: Planning and validation:** planning was completed in March 2023. Validation and periodical reviews are ongoing till the end of the project.
- **CC1.2: Pre-Acceleration:** The first pre-acceleration round concluded (April 2024 – September 2024), as did the second pre-acceleration round (June 2024 – December 2024).. (task leader: UniVE)
- **CC1.3: Acceleration:** The first acceleration cycle (April 2024 – September 2024) has concluded, while the second cycle is about to begin, starting in mid-January 2025 and ending in June 2025. (task leader: UniVR)
- **CC1.4: Fundraising:** The first Fundraising cycle is occurring (task leader: UniTS)

The objectives of Task **CC1.1** were concluded by outlining common actions for all participating spokes. A common strategy was provided for all 9 spokes, planned through scheduled meetings and constant communication through online data-sharing platforms.

The first two **pre-acceleration (CC1.2)** rounds have successfully concluded, coordinated by Dr. Serena Ruffato, the scouting specialist hired under a contract effective March 1. Dr. Ruffato spearheaded the call for startup pre-seed initiatives for Spoke 4, conducting extensive scouting activities within the Università Iuav di Venezia through various initiatives and events. Spoke 4 capitalized on the strong reputation of the Start.Hub Iuav program—a well-established idea acceleration pathway at Iuav—to attract, refine, and select 10–15 promising ideas per cycle.

In the **first Acceleration (CC1.3)** cycle, two startups proposed by Spoke 4 were selected: Re-Hub and ARGO. Re-Hub advanced to the fourth **Fundraising** phase (**CC1.4**), where it received the special prize awarded by Gellify during the investor day.

Spoke 4 has not been represented by any startups in the **second Acceleration (CC1.3)** cycle.

4.2. SPOKE 4 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke 4

Background / State of the Art:

Since 2017, IUAV has organised a training and idea-acceleration program for students, alumni, PhD students, researchers, and collaborators every year. The goal is to enhance ideas born within undergraduate, doctoral or master's workshops with high business potential and/or elevated technological and innovative value and turn them into academic spinoffs.

The program is structured in two phases:

1. Startup School - training course on entrepreneurship

The training activity aims to promote entrepreneurial literacy through the analysis of successful cases, best practices, and opportunities emerging from society. The focus is on assessing the impact of the idea on the context and the importance of the team for the technical and economic sustainability of the project. Startup school is organised, with open meetings for everyone to attend. Course attendance allows students to earn university credits and LinkedIn badges.

Classes are held in-person and online and involve expert teachers in business and startups. Face-to-face training sessions are alternated with workshop sessions for analysis and development of ideas, encouraging cross-fertilisation among participants. CEOs of experienced and successful startups are also invited to bring their experience and feedback.

2. Start. Hub - ideas acceleration program

A maximum of 12/14 teams, formed/consolidated during the Startup School training period, will access the second part of the program. Every team must meet specific criteria: have an innovative idea, consist of at least two members, and one must be affiliated (in the present or the past) with IUAV.

The course includes project work days, which are divided into groups and supported by a mentor who follows all stages of project development. The last meeting is structured as an intensive residential workshop, alternating face-to-face didactic activities, group analytical work, and one-on-one meetings with experts in marketing, business, administration, IT, user experience, product, patent, legal, etc.

At the end of the course, there is a pitch competition in which teams present their ideas and prototypes to an audience of investors, institutions and companies that decide the five winners who are awarded a cash prize to invest in the business idea.

Methodology:

The pre-acceleration funnel shared horizontally among all the Spokes of CCI is divided into the following steps:

1. **Target engagement, Scouting and Pre-screening.** Are performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. **Screening and Committee evaluation.** The scouting specialists suggest a short list of 4/5 startups. The CCI Committee selected 40 teams among the 9 Spokes.
3. **Selection Day.** During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CCI Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10-15 teams for the Acceleration phase.

Spoke 4 adapted the Start.Hub idea acceleration program to align with the terms and timelines of the iNEST CCI funnel, using it as a tool available to the scouting specialist for selecting the best business ideas within its spoke.

In the second pre-acceleration cycle, 10 ideas/startups were generated from the two editions of Start.Hub 2022/23.

The second pre-acceleration cycle funnel

In the third cycle, the Scouting Specialist conducted a series of targeted activities aimed at promoting and collecting new ideas. The strategy involved anticipating the immersive week by integrating the scouting phase with the pre-screening phase. During the immersive week, held at the end of March, a team composed of the Scouting Specialist and ten professionals had the opportunity to delve deeper into the selected ideas, working to refine and consolidate the underlying business models.

The third pre-acceleration cycle funnel

As in the previous cycle, the "Start.Hub LAB" was established as a dedicated physical space within Luav University to enhance target engagement. This space serves as a permanent hub for connecting with individuals interested in the initiative. In addition to continuous online support, both current and

aspiring entrepreneurs benefit from an environment designed to encourage idea exchange and foster dialogue among scouting specialists, students, and other stakeholders. To further promote the initiative, the CCI team organised a series of presentations across bachelor's, master's, and doctoral programs, actively engaging both professors and students.

Nov 24 - Jan 25 > The [call for ideas](#) was opened in November 2024 and remained open until early February 2025. The call for ideas was disseminated through the institutional channels of iNEST and the Università Luav di Venezia, with the support of the technology transfer office. The call for ideas collected 81 expressions of interest from students, alumni, and researchers interested in exploring themes related to self-entrepreneurship.

Jan 25 - Feb 25 > Through the [Startup School](#), an integral part of the Start.Hub Luav program, more than 75 participants were trained through lessons on self-entrepreneurship, idea analysis using the design thinking methodology, and facilitating the matching of participants to form heterogeneous and multidisciplinary teams. The Scouting Specialist coordinated the activities with the support of a team of teachers, mentors and experts. The Startup School generated around 21 business ideas.

Mar 25 > Compared to the previous cycle, and to strengthen and refine business ideas ahead of the acceleration phase—while also conducting a careful selection of the most deserving teams—the Scouting Specialist organised an [immersive weekend](#) event called the *Startup Bootcamp*, held from March 28 to 30, 2025. The bootcamp focused on validating entrepreneurial ideas in the fields of urban innovation, architecture, design, and sustainable fashion. Ten teams, selected from the participants of the START.HUB School Luav had the opportunity to work side by side with industry experts, refine their business concepts, and spend three days at the beautiful Villa Angaran San Giuseppe in Bassano del Grappa.

Ongoing activities:

Sep 2025 – Nov 2025

The same 10 teams that took part in the immersive weekend will join the [Start.Hub acceleration program](#). Throughout the sessions, each team will be paired with mentors and experts who will help develop the business idea further, analyse competitors, prepare a compelling pitch deck, and draft an executive summary of the project.

A second bootcamp will be organised in mid-October as an intensive workshop, where teams will meet technical experts and mentors who will help them fill gaps in their skill sets. Before the bootcamp, with support from the Scouting Specialist and the use of analytical tools, each team will identify their specific needs in order to match with the most suitable mentors or instructors.

Nov 2025

At the end of the program, the 10 teams will compete in a [pitch competition](#) to identify the top 5 business ideas. The event will take place at Luav Badoer. The Scouting Specialist will support the five selected teams in preparing their pitch decks, facilitate connections with investors and/or business partners, and guide them through the startup founding process.

[Focus on Task CCI.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 4](#)

Background/State of the Art

In the first cycle, two of the ten startups presented by Spoke 4 were selected to participate in the training and acceleration program coordinated across all the Spokes in the Triveneto region.

Rehub and Argo actively participated in all the training sessions held in the area. They benefited from the support of tutors and instructors to improve their pitch decks and refine the business models of their entrepreneurial ideas. The first cycle concluded with the Demo Day in Verona on October 25, 2024. A panel of seven investors evaluated the ideas. Rehub was awarded the special prize offered by Gellify.

On the second cycle, only one of the five projects, Farma 282, successfully passed the selection for the selection day. Unfortunately, none of the startups proposed by Spoke 4 advanced to the acceleration phase.

Methodology:

The iNEST acceleration program was structured as a series of monthly two-day in-person meetings (Friday and Saturday), hosted on a rotational basis at one of the locations provided by each Spoke. In the second cycle, Spoke 4 was not represented by any startup. The scouting specialist attended the in-person sessions to network and support the accelerated teams.

Below is the schedule of meetings for the second round of acceleration:

- Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento (UniTS): “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”
- Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, actual solution and proposal”
- Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”
- Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (UniVE): “Governance, mission & vision, strategy, business model; tools for AI”
- Pitch Clinic: April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav)
- Workshop #5: May 9-10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & Eco-Fin Plan”
- Workshop #6: May 23-24, 2025, in Trieste, “Eco-Fin Plan & funding”
- Pitch Clinic: June 6, 2025, in Verona
- Demo Day: June 26 2025, 2024, in Venice (UniVE)

For the third cycle, still ongoing, a demo day and direct comparison with the competitions of other Spokes are not planned.

However, Spoke 4 has committed to continuing the selection process as a best practice, implementing adjustments and improvements informed by experience and cross-learning with other Spokes.

The 10 teams selected for the training program are composed of highly experienced individuals, including researchers, PhD candidates, and university professors. These are more technical profiles, actively involved in the development of the startups, and were recruited through significant outreach and dissemination efforts.

The outcomes of this third phase appear promising, not only in terms of the teams' experience but also in the maturity, economic viability, and technical soundness of the business ideas.

4.3. SPOKE 4 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

To strengthen scouting efforts and the dissemination of activities, targeted interventions were carried out within the design laboratories of IUAV University. These interventions aimed to promote the Start.Hub 2024/25 program and inform students about the opportunities available upon its completion.

Traditional engagement techniques were used for scouting, including one-on-one meetings, events organised in collaboration with the doctoral school to raise awareness among PhD holders, PhD candidates, and research fellows, as well as classroom presentations and dissemination activities.

The most significant dissemination events are listed below:

- Open Call: **Start.Hub School**
<https://www.iuavspinoff.it/starthubschool25/>
Nov 25 - Feb 18 - Online (Typeform)
Spoke 4 collected 81 expressions of interest for participation in the Start.Hub School program through a Typeform submission.
- Workshop: **Start.Hub School**
<https://www.iuavspinoff.it/starthubschool25/>
Feb 19, March 4-12, Apr 9 - Cotonificio Santa Marta Iuav Venice
START.HUB School organised four in-person sessions between February and April 2025 at Cotonificio Santa Marta, providing participants with an overview of self-entrepreneurship and presenting the role of the consortium and opportunities for startups.
- CC4 Event: **Raccontare le strade dell'innovazione del veneto**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/raccontare-le-strade-dellinnovazione-del-veneto-verso-unapp-a-servizio-del-territorio/>
March 19, 2024 - Villa Filanda Antonini in Villorba (Treviso)
On January 17, 2025, the event was part of the Citizen Engagement activities promoted by the iNEST CC4 – Spoke 4 project. The event includes an introductory session followed by a hands-on workshop that brings together companies, local authorities, tourism and cultural operators, and citizens. The goal is to co-design an interactive and informative app and explore possible development paths along the region's strategic road networks.
CCI of Spoke 4 was also involved in the initiative through the participation of the Scouting Specialist, who contributed to the working table "Target Users and Dissemination/Marketing" to facilitate idea generation and help translate the research developed by the curators into a potential business idea to be submitted to the Start.Hub program.
- Open call: **"Start.Hub Bootcamp"**
<https://www.consorzioinest.it/start-hub-bootcamp/>
Feb 25 - Mar 25- Online (Typeform)
Spoke 4 promoted and disseminated an open call for participation in the intensive Start.Hub Bootcamp workshop, which received around fifteen applications. A panel of experts, composed of the iNEST CCI Scientific Coordinator and the START.HUB team, selected the top 10 participating teams based on two main criteria: the innovativeness of the idea and the solidity of the team.
- Workshop: **"Start.Hub Bootcamp"**
<https://www.iuavspinoff.it/start-hub-bootcamp-diario/>
Mar 28-30- Villa Angaran San Giuseppe (Treviso)

The 10 selected teams took on the challenge of developing their innovative ideas in the fields of urban planning, architecture, design, and sustainable fashion. They had the opportunity to work closely with tutors, professors, and experts from the startup and business worlds to refine

their entrepreneurial projects and strengthen key skills, making their ideas more solid and competitive.

4.4. SPOKE 4 CCI MAIN RESULTS

Although none of the startups from Spoke 4 advanced to the fundraising stage, the Scouting Specialist committed to continuing support activities for the startups that didn't pass the selection and to strengthening the new recruits.

One of the most interesting outcomes of this phase was the program's ability to **engage a more mature and technically skilled target group**.

In previous editions, the absence of key profiles such as researchers, PhD candidates, and university professors within the project teams had been noted as a major gap, limiting the teams' technical depth and know-how. In this round of dissemination and scouting, however, 4 out of the 10 selected teams include one or more of these profiles. Their presence not only strengthens the startups from a technical standpoint but also fosters deeper engagement and determination within the teams.

Another positive outcome emerged from the **way teams were engaged and encouraged to collaborate** during the Start.Hub School sessions and the Bootcamp.

Some teams, initially composed of just one or two members, decided to merge into stronger, unified teams after discovering overlapping goals and complementary ideas through joint discussions. This was made possible thanks to the strong matching efforts led by Start.Hub team, coordinated by the Scouting Specialist, as well as through one-on-one meetings with experts. One of the key methods implemented during the working sessions involved the use of a shared MIRO board. Teams were invited to present their ideas using visual and summary cards, allowing peers to explore each other's projects, build connections, and launch calls to action aimed at integrating their teams with professional or academic profiles they needed.

MIRO Board Snapshot – Start.Hub Collaborative Space

As outlined in the previous report, a positive outcome was generated by creating a **coordination team** that involved the **research fellows responsible for the four cross-cutting activities** within Spoke 4. In particular, the scouting specialist benefited from the experience and support of fellow researchers in organising events dedicated to startups. Spoke 4 will continue to pursue this idea of cross-pollination by organising joint and cross-disciplinary events in the future involving CC1, CC2, CC3, and CC4.

4.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

The scouting activities for the second round were much more structured than the first, following a well-defined workflow that allowed for broader audience engagement.

However, while the startups selected and presented during the first round of pre-screening were already well-established with solid business foundations, the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and BRL (Business Readiness Level) of the business ideas gathered in the second round were insufficient to compete with the proposals from other Spokes. None of these ideas managed to pass the screening phase.

Spoke 4 has recently made a targeted effort to engage more mature and specialised profiles by collaborating with the Technology Transfer Office. This involved mapping ongoing research results, thesis projects, PhD dissertations, and research initiatives led by university faculty members.

Despite a lower numerical success of the initiative (81 expressions of interest compared to 206 in the previous edition, and 21 ideas generated compared to 31 previously), the quality and solidity of the ideas were noticeably higher. This indicates that the program is gaining its own identity and credibility, attracting only truly motivated teams.

The combination of know-how from students across different disciplines has the potential to generate entrepreneurial projects with high technological value, strong growth prospects, and scalability—core qualities of successful startups. The objective is to build more diverse teams by integrating design and project skills with business strategy and technological expertise, ultimately increasing the competitiveness of future proposals.

4.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The primary objective will be to strengthen the startups that did not pass the pre-selection phase by providing tailored support to refine and develop their business models.

The issue of skill gaps remains a challenge—particularly for Spoke 4 at a design-focused university like luav

where it's difficult to bridge the divide between creative ideas and their technical or business feasibility. There is still limited awareness of market opportunities for research projects and of the potential to turn product or service concepts into viable business ideas.

Clearly, further efforts are needed to raise awareness. However, what's also lacking is stronger interaction with more technically and economically grounded environments.

In the coming months, Spoke 4 will implement a series of actions aimed at involving professionals from outside the luav University as mentors or consultants for startups. These will include targeted one-on-one meetings and open calls addressed to external stakeholders.

The goal is not only to generate disruptive ideas with high social and environmental impact, but also to ensure these ideas have the technical and economic solidity necessary to compete with those developed at other universities.

The results of this experimental approach will be evaluated after the final phase of the project in November 2025.

5. SPOKE 5 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 5 address current issues related to **Smart and sustainable environments (manufacturing, working, living)**.

These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - New and Emerging Technologies for Human Centric Manufacturing and other industrial working environment**
- **RT2 - Digital Twin in Industries 5.0**
- **RT3 - People, organization, and processes for Industry 5.0**
- **RT4 - Personalized Assistive Technologies and Smart Environments for Inclusive Living in private and public spaces**

Within this framework, **cross-cutting activity 1** is relevant to support the development of new business ideas from research through a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, the cross-cutting activity 1 is oriented to sustain the identification and valorization of innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 5 connected to the relationship between digitalization and sustainability in different environments, by facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

5.1. SPOKE 5 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Objectives and key results

The Spoke's shared goal is the development of innovative, smart, sustainable, digitally-driven working and living environments within a human-centric design framework.

In this respect, the CC1 objective is to identify and develop innovative ideas related to the different research topics connected with the focus of Spoke 5, specifically related to the nexus between physical and digital worlds, shaped by digitalization and new technological tools and where social sustainability ("human-centered" manufacturing and living environments) is concerned.

This is a wide area of research that can generate business ideas from different research streams, such as those related to technological trajectories and data collection and exploitation in an Industry 5.0 perspectives; new applications in the human-machine interface; context of innovative (smart, sustainable) environments, and many more potentially scoutable.

The cross-cutting activity 1 aims specifically to contribute to the innovation ecosystem promoting the scouting of innovative ideas connected of the past and current research of the different actors involved in the Spoke 5 in order to select most promising ones for the acceleration activities and funding opportunity.

Objectives also refer also to:

- increasing the awareness of researchers of potential business applications of research results to new entrepreneurial activities promoted by researchers and test them in multiple forms (business model generations, proof-of-concept)

- enhancing the possibility to launch spin-offs rooted on academic research to continue the exploitation of relationship between research and innovation and business applications
- favoring the exploitation of research results (e.g. patents) existing at the Spoke 5 level converting them into new start-ups and spin-offs

5.2. SPOKE 5 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- **CC1.3: Acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase..
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40

- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. the objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 15-32
- **CC1.4: Fundraising**
 - Sub Task CC1.4.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNITS
Duration: months 15-40
 - Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage to support investment-ready scaleups fulfilling their financial needs. This task includes creating a comprehensive business plan that outlines the Start Up's goals, strategies, and financial projections. It should also involve identifying and approaching potential investors, including venture capital firms, and negotiating/structuring investment deals.
Responsible: UNITS
Duration: months 21-34
 - Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage. The goal of this task is to provide skills, identify tools and evaluate market strategies to support scale-ups towards their final Exit-IPO or Trade-Sale
Responsible: UNIPD
Duration: months 23-40

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and pre-acceleration activities in the Spoke "5"

Background / State of the Art:

- Structured set of activities at the University (Spoke 5 coordinator) level related to the support of spin-off development and engagement for growth
- Established initiatives for entrepreneurial development targeting researchers and students
- Partnership and collaboration with key actors at the national level for technological transfer and spin-off generations
- Experience in innovative training

Methodology:

- **Partnership with selected providers** for the co-design and delivery of tailored training and awareness-raising events focused on research valorisation and entrepreneurial mindset development
- **Distribution and analysis of engagement questionnaires** to participants in all activities, aimed at assessing satisfaction levels and identifying potential for follow-up or targeted support
- **Competence mapping and comparison of entrepreneurial needs** in relation to the specific challenges and innovation domains of Spoke 5
- **Proactive patent screening** conducted within the University's proprietary database to identify relevant patents and internal research groups working on topics aligned with the project's

strategic areas; the activity was fully managed and executed by Spoke 5 as part of its internal scouting methodology

- **Continuous multi-level coordination with internal partners** operating within Spoke 5 (e.g., research centres, incubators, TTOs), aimed at fostering synergies, improving alignment, and facilitating the identification of promising start-ups and their matching with the most appropriate scaling and support paths.
- **Collaborative data-driven review with innovation research project funding managers** within Spoke 5, focused on funded research initiatives. Regular exchanges were carried out to analyse project data, validate scouting directions, and support decision-making processes by identifying synergies and confirming the strategic relevance of selected ideas and teams.
- **Creation of a dedicated batch of promising pre-acceleration projects** that were not selected for the acceleration phase. A structured follow-up strategy was designed to monitor their progress over time and assess potential support actions, through scheduled catch-up meetings and personalized guidance pathways aimed at reactivating or redirecting their development trajectory.

Final Activities and Results

The following section summarizes the full range of activities and achievements carried out throughout the entire duration of the project – covering two rounds of Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration (January 2024 – June 2025) – with specific updates related to support activities for the final phase – Fundraising – which is still ongoing until the official end of the project (December 2025).

- Delivered a comprehensive activity plan for scouting and spin-off development, including clearly defined phases and KPIs
- Carried out a targeted mapping and engagement campaign, resulting in a validated pipeline of ideas and researcher profiles.
- Coordinated the selection process in collaboration with the CC1 scientific group, ensuring consistency in evaluation criteria and alignment across support pathways.
- Appointed and deployed two scouting specialists who conducted one-to-one interviews and follow-up sessions and actively contributed to both the Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration programmes.
- Organised and completed a series of online meetings with researchers, aimed at fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and promoting the valorisation of research outcomes.

The activities listed above are now described in greater detail below.

ROUND 1 PRE-ACCELERATION – January 2024 – MAY 2024

Selection Day: 19th March 2024

In the first round of startup selection, **Spoke 5** focused on identifying high-potential teams already emerging within UniPD, thanks to various initiatives and activities dedicated to research entrepreneurship and startup/spin-off creation such as StartCup Padova, StartCup Veneto, and the Contamination Lab.

The outreach and engagement activities targeting two main groups

Spin-offs from the University of Padua and **participants in StartCup competitions** generated the following results:

- **Initial contacts** were established with 23 spin-offs and 10 StartCup participants.
- Among these, **11 spin-offs** and **7 StartCup participants** expressed interest in taking part in the programme.
- A total of **8 spin-offs** and **5 StartCup participants** went on to complete the application form.

- Finally, **3 proposals** from spin-offs and **2 from StartCup participants** were submitted for final selection.
- Ultimately 2 startups - STAT4VALUE and BBSof - from the cohort identified within UNIPD's ecosystem were admitted to the Accelerator programme.

This data highlights a progressive filtering process from initial outreach to final proposal submission, with a comparable level of engagement between the two groups.

This first round of pre-acceleration for UNIPD resulted in the selection of the following 2 startups:

- **STAT4VALUE:** software platform to support companies in data analysis and its use for decision-making.
- **BBSof:** software for monitoring movements in sports settings, aimed at evaluating performance and injury risk.

ROUND 2 PRE-ACCELERATION June 2024 – Nov 2024

Selection Day: Dec 3rd 2024

In the second round of startup selection, Spoke 5 (UNIPD) adopted a more structured methodology compared to the first cycle, while maintaining the same ultimate goal: to present a group of high-potential entrepreneurial ideas at the **Selection Day on December 3rd**, with a view to admitting them into the **Acceleration Program scheduled for the first half of 2025**.

The **pre-acceleration phase**, launched in **May 2024**, followed two main approaches:

- A so-called **“hunting” strategy**, which involved analysing top-performing university researchers based on successful funded research projects, a detailed review of university patent databases, and leveraging existing initiatives and contacts promoting startups — such as StartCup Padova 2024, promising non-selected projects from StartCup Veneto 2023 (first round), and collaboration with network partner T2i to cover the Treviso-Rovigo area.
- A **“fishing” strategy**, which focused on distributing a dedicated call for interest via the regular **Spin-off Office Newsletter** of the University of Padua.

The work of the Scouting Specialists was primarily focused on the following activities:

- **Mapping:** creation of a contact list based on the various sources mentioned above
- **Outreach:** initial contact via email or phone to assess interest in participating
- **Follow-up:** interaction through video calls with co-founders/researchers to further explore the entrepreneurial idea
- **Coaching:** once the most interested and motivated teams were identified, coaching calls were organised to help better structure the business idea and pitch deck in preparation for the Selection Day.

Initial Outreach and Contact Mapping

All contacts made, regardless of outcome or response.

62 spin-offs have been contacted through a customized newsletter.

11 patents owners inventor or team/spin-off have been contacted

10 start-ups participating in STARTCUP PADOVA have been contacted

Engaged Leads and Next Steps

Contacts that progressed to follow-up interactions — including meetings, coaching, and selection outcomes:

- 20 spin-offs

- 5 start-up ideas (ECOBOT, SYNARGY, VERITÀ, SHOPFLOW, AIRFARM) supported and selected by Spoke5 SS and SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE
- 3 R&D champions Accepted to the Acceleration stage: ECOBOT, SYNARGY and AIRFARM.

INSIGHT ON PATENTS - Spoke 5

Collection process designed and managed by SS uniPD

FOREWORD

- There emerged a need to test a different approach to startup scouting for the acceleration programme, in parallel with the “call for ideas”. This alternative approach focuses on identifying technologies within the university’s patent portfolio that could be enhanced through entrepreneurial projects.
- Starting from the **Knowledge Share platform (<https://www.knowledge-share.eu/it>)**, Spoke5’s Scouting Officers conducted a search for the most relevant patents, using selected keywords related to the themes of the spoke.

STEPS

- Prompt of keywords on KnowledgeShare (KS): selection of keywords and filters, aligned with the iNEST macro-themes. KS filtering categories: Research centres – Keywords – Categories - Trend sectors
- Possible cross-check with other platforms: KS offers limited filtering options. Other platforms can be used to access technical details of the patents (authors, dates, stage, technical-legal aspects, etc.): PatentLens, Espacenet, Orbit
- Analysis of output: Assessment of individual patent records.
Total UniPD patents on KS: 102
Total UniPD patents since 1995: 425, of which 20 are from 2023 (3 of which have been transferred — source: university database)
- Discussion with TTO: This phase of IP market intelligence helps assess the maturity level of the patent and the market’s response to it (e.g. transfers or royalties).
- Contact with inventors: Contact and dialogue with internal and external inventors through a semi-structured interview, aimed at understanding their willingness to initiate an entrepreneurial valorisation process.
- Assessment (GO / NO GO): Considerations regarding: willingness and motivation of researcher/professor, TRL/BRL, interest in CCI and, in the case of GO, support from Scouting Specialists

Search Type	Number of Records	Titles
KEYWORDS	400	
CATEGORIES	23	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aerospace 2. Agritech & Foodtech 3. Other 4. Environment & Sustainability 5. Arts & Culture 6. Automotive & Transportation 7. Banking, Financial Services & Insurance 8. Chemistry & Advanced Materials 9. Cosmetics, Nutraceuticals & Supplements 10. Buildings, Construction & Architecture 11. Education & Awareness 12. Energy & Power Systems 13. ESG, Risk Management & Welfare 14. Industry 4.0 15. IT & Telecommunications Systems 16. Machinery & Equipment 17. Robotics

		18. Health & Biomedical 19. Semiconductors & Electronics 20. Innovation Services 21. Space Economy 22. Sport & Fitness 23. Retail & eCommerce
TRENDS	16	1. Three, Two, One: We Make Future 2024 – KS With You! 2. IoT and AI Applications in Industry 3. BIOVARIA: Candidate Technologies 4. Circular Economy: Creating New from the Old 5. Fighting Cancer One Tech at a Time 6. COP 27 – UN Climate Change Summit 7. COVID-19 Response: To Detect, Mitigate and Destroy the Virus 8. IPA 2021 – Award for Excellence in Italian Public Research 9. Improving Our Agricultural Practices 10. Plastics: Recovery, Recycling, Alternatives and Cradle-to-Cradle Solutions 11. Assistive and Rehabilitative Robotics 12. Safeguarding Our Water: From Production to Purification and Management 13. Energy Transition: Batteries, Storage, Smart Grids and Management Systems 14. Green and Sustainable Transport of the Future – TSD 2021 15. Environmentally Sound Technologies 16. Towards Zero Impact and Recycling

Research Areas / Keywords	Number of Patents	Titles
SMART HOME e SMART DEVICE	6	1. Redox Flow Battery Management System – BMS 2. Compartmentalized Tank and Stack for Redox Flow Batteries 3. Intelligent Solar Shading 4. Smart Pot for Induction Cooktop 5. Safety System for Smart Devices 6. Coffee and Other Hot Beverage Machine for Induction Cooktop
MANUFACTURING	11	1. Storage and Reconversion of Electrical Energy 2. Rotor for Synchronous Reluctance Motor 3. Microplastic Filter in Household Appliances 4. Innovative High-Performance Insulator for Electric Motors 5. Functionalization of Nanostructures

PATENTS IDENTIFIED	INVENTOR GROUPS CONTACTED	CONTACTS ACTIVATED	CONTACTS ON HOLD	CONTACTS WITHOUT RESPONSE
11	9	3 (33%)	1	5

DETAIL CONTACTS ACTIVATED

Patent 1 – Year 2020

Redox Flow Battery Management System – BMS - TRL 7

Description: This innovative electronic system (Battery Management System - BMS) was developed to optimise the management of redox flow batteries used in renewable energy power plants or within electrical grids.

Possible Applications:

- Industrial systems with redox flow batteries (RFB);
- Management, control, and characterisation system for flow batteries used in energy storage systems supporting advanced electrical grids (smart grids, microgrids);
- Testing laboratories for RFBs.

Advantages:

- Ensures fast response times;
- Extends battery lifespan;
- Manages multiple batteries simultaneously;
- Reduces maintenance costs;
- Guarantees maximum charge-discharge efficiency.

Patent 2 – Year 2019

Intelligent Solar Shading - TRL (N/A)

Description: This solar shading system improves the energy performance of buildings by controlling solar radiation on vertical surfaces through an automated movement system of shading panels. The system is based on internal and external temperature parameters and indoor lighting levels. Modular, flexible, and scalable, it can be installed on both new and refurbished buildings.

Possible Applications:

- Solar shading of vertical surfaces of buildings in temperate climate zones;
- Suitable for new buildings or renovations;
- Applicable to individual openings or entire façades.

Advantages:

- Improves the energy performance of buildings;
- Automated: the optimal shading position is adjusted based on internal and external temperature and lighting parameters;
- Modular: single shading elements can be repeated;
- Flexible: small system modifications allow adaptation of the modularity;
- Scalable: suitable for individual openings or glazed façades;
- Customisable: different finishes on shading surfaces can enhance architectural appearance;
- Compliant with UNI EN 13363 standard.

Patent 3 – Year 2021

Innovative High-Performance Insulator for Electric Motors - TRL 4

Description: This invention relates to a new coating methodology for the copper conductors of electric motors, which not only protects them by providing optimal electromagnetic insulation but also offers high chemical resistance (e.g., against corrosion) and thermal resistance up to temperatures exceeding 600°C.

Possible Applications:

- Automotive sector, electric motors: energy recovery from automotive turbochargers;
- Aeronautical sector: useful in start-up and energy generation with gas turbines.

Advantages:

- Increases the operating temperature range of an electric motor;
- Facilitates the manufacturing and installation process of insulators;
- Creates more stable and long-lasting insulation compared to standard applications;
- Eliminates the need for active cooling systems, thus saving energy;
- Enhances performance of electric motors operating in thermally challenging environments (high temperatures);
- Improves resistance to corrosive phenomena.

CONCLUSIONS

This initial test aimed to evaluate whether patent research can help identify ideas with potential for development and scaling. Although the sample assessed so far is limited, the following observations were made:

- The link between patent and idea scalability is never direct, even if the patent appears strong on paper.
- Inventors' interest often focuses more on finding partners and funding to achieve the next step and/or maintain the patent active (due to high maintenance costs), rather than on scaling the idea.
- The patent is one component (often not the predominant one) in the creation of innovative startups and the entrepreneurial journey, which requires alignment with other essential factors (e.g., a motivated team, an attractive market, etc.).

INSIGHT ON FUNDING - Spoke 5

Template proposal for collection for individual Spokes (CS and SS) proposed by unIVE

One of the approaches suggested by the scouting group established within the CC1 activity to identify promising startup ideas involves analysing the university's R&D portfolio, with the aim of identifying high-performing researchers, departments, or research groups.

Thanks to the collaboration with the Grant Office of the University of Padua, we obtained a database of European R&D projects (focused on the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes) in which the university is involved. Given the large volume of data, we present below a preliminary analysis. The dataset provides an overview of external research funding received by the university under the Horizon 2020 programme. The main table details each funded project, including the call ID, type of funding, total grant, and the share allocated to the university. Additional pivot tables break down funding by department and by funding instrument.

Potential for Research Valorisation:

It would be valuable to analyse the progress of the projects in which UniPd is involved and assess the potential for exploiting research outcomes. In particular, it could be useful to identify which projects have the potential to generate university spin-offs, thereby contributing to technology transfer and innovation within the economic and industrial landscape.

Overall, the data highlight the university's strong commitment to EU-funded research, with notable excellence in the fields of engineering, physics, and biomedicine, and a significant ability to attract funding through competitive calls.

The discussion with the Grant Office at the University of Padua highlighted several PIs who have been particularly active in securing funding and could be considered for future outreach.

Just under 20 individuals including Full Professors, Associate Professors, Researchers, and PhD candidates have been identified as potentially relevant based on the type of projects they are developing.

The fields involved include Civil and Environmental Engineering, Physics, Industrial Engineering, Forestry and Agriculture, Biomedical Sciences, Psychology, and Chemistry.

At the end of the selection process, the startups chosen to pitch at the **Selection Day on December 3rd** aiming for admission to the acceleration programme starting in early 2025, are:

1. **SYNARGY**
2. **AIRFARM**
3. **ECOBOT**
4. **SHOPFLOW**
5. **VERITÀ**

SYNARGY and **AIRFARM** were selected from the pool of candidates participating in **StartCup Padova 2024**. Notably, SYNARGY ranked **first overall** in the competition.

SHOPFLOW was selected among the candidates from **StartCup Veneto 2023**. It had already taken part in the **first round of the iNEST Selection Day**, but was not selected at that time.

ECOBOT was suggested directly by Scouting Officer for the CC1 activity, who recommended reaching out to **Prof. Menegatti** from UniPD. Interestingly, Prof. Menegatti also stood out in the analysis of top-performing profiles in terms of success rate and impact of internationally funded research projects.

VERITÀ was proposed by a scouting specialist from the iNEST project (**Spoke 9 – SISSA Trieste**), who suggested contacting the student behind the startup idea. It was later discovered that the same law student from UniPD had also participated in the **Contamination Lab 2024**, where he met and collaborated with another student (a computer science major) who is now acting as **CTO** of the project.

As a result of the Selection Day, **three UniPD projects were selected** for the 2 round of Acceleration

**Synargy,
Airfarm,
ECOBOT.**

The two projects that were **not selected**, although valuable, have expressed their intention to continue developing their entrepreneurial ideas. In December, we held a **follow-up call with the Shopflow team**, reflecting on the reasons behind the non-selection and discussing their next steps.

For all the others non-selected

- ICS – Inside Climate Service
- SmartSkin: this startup idea comes **from the patent screening** methodology
- Biocsyn
- Bookycare
- Direct from Italy
- Be Like You
- Opigeo
- Mamma Cocca
- BookPlate/Autheticity

the Scouting Specialists have identified, for each non-selected startup, specific needs and opportunities for targeted support. This support may involve collaboration with relevant university departments when appropriate. Among these startups, some are particularly advanced spinoffs with established structures and a significant market presence in terms of revenue and resource allocation. These entities require focused assistance to facilitate growth, often through access to substantial funding or the recruitment of experienced professionals, aimed at accelerating the scaling of their business models.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities in the Spoke “5”

Background/State of the Art: Sub-task CC1.3.1 and Sub-task CC1.3.2 have been developed by other partner and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns Sub-task CC1.3.3, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For Sub-task CC1.3.3, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

ROUND 1 ACCELERATION April 24 - October 24 –

The path to the final Demo day: October 25th 2024 was based on the following set of events:

- Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
- Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
- Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
- Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
- Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
- Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l’Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Filì from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

WORKSHOPS

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions. The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
- Webinar #2: Marketing, customer acquisition, sales (June 24, 2024) by Giacomo Tesolin;
- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;

- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

UNIPD's scouting specialist provided also contribution in mentoring and supporting three early-stage startups—Discovera, Sindrel, and SEP—throughout the first iNEST acceleration programme. The contribution focused on evolving from early concepts to more structured, investor-ready ventures. The support was provided through 1:1 coaching sessions, participation in 5 workshops, and continuous feedback on pitch materials, market fit, and IP valorization strategies.

- Discovera: Initially positioned as a computational service provider for drug discovery, Discovera pivoted to a more ambitious business model focused on developing proprietary drug candidates using their AI-driven in silico platform. UNIPD's team supported the startup in redefining their go-to-market approach, clarifying their IP strategy, and developing a robust financial model and roadmap for fundraising, including alignment with programs like Smart&Start and potential EU Pathfinder grants.
- Sindrel: With a patented, programmable drug delivery system, Sindrel was one of the most technically complex projects in the cohort. UNIPD's coach guided the team in mapping the best pharmaceutical applications for their technology, engaged them in an open innovation challenge with Angelini Pharma, and helped refine both the pitch and the business model to better highlight the value proposition for industrial partnerships. He also advised on collaborative R&D grants, in view of future clinical and regulatory steps.
- SEP (Smart Environment Platform): For SEP, a startup focused on monitoring and predicting pathogen outbreaks, the scouting specialist facilitated a matchmaking process with a hospital to support user need validation and contextual use-case definition. He also supported efforts to refine the business model, develop a more focused value proposition across market verticals (healthcare, veterinary, environmental monitoring), and improve the communication strategy of the pitch deck.

Results: All three startups demonstrated significant progress over the course of the programme. At the final Demo Day held in Verona (October 2024), Sindrel ranked 1st and Discovera 3rd based on jury evaluation, confirming the quality of their advancements. The work done laid strong foundations for further development, partnership building, and future fundraising.

ROUND 2 ACCELERATION Jan 25 – June 25

The path to the final Demo day in June 26th 2025 was based on the following set of events:

- Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
- Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
- Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
- Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca' Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
- Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (luav).
- Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
- Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
- Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

The 2nd cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Venezia on June 26, 2025.

Between April and June 2025, UNIPD's coach provided structured mentoring and strategic advisory to three research-based startups: Synargy, Algae Scope and, to help other coach to support also FENIX. Across the period, he delivered a total of 16 targeted coaching sessions, tailored to the maturity and sector-specific challenges of each team.

- Synargy (biotech – gene therapy for kidney cancer): the coach supported the startup in shaping its business model, clarifying its IP strategy, and developing a preliminary financial and fundraising roadmap. He guided the team through several iterations of the strategic plan and pitch, provided input on pre-clinical milestones, and contributed to the formulation of a clear investor narrative. He also developed and delivered a custom exit strategy presentation with NPV/IRR simulations and licensing revenue assumptions.
- Algae Scope (bio-based materials and bioethanol): Mentoring focused on validating the go-to-market approach, assessing the dual-product strategy (coatings and bioethanol), and navigating governance complexities among co-founders. The coach provided strategic advice on how to position the company in both the sustainability and bioenergy sectors, reviewed multiple versions of the business plan, and helped shape the funding strategy.
- FENIX (construction sector – circular economy): Support included early-stage investor readiness coaching, review of the techno-economic model, and refinement of the value proposition for customers and partners. Discussions also covered regulatory considerations tied to “End-of-Waste” certification pathways for recycled materials.

The startups mentored achieved notable success: Synargy and Algae Scope ranked first and second, respectively, at the Demo Day, validating the impact of the coaching programme.

Focus on Task CC1.4: Fundraising activities in the Spoke “5”

Between April and June 2025, the UniPd team with specific involvement of Prof. Claudia Sandei design and implement legal support services as part of the iNEST CC1 activities, under the framework of the Legal Sanity Check initiative. This initiative aimed to provide early-stage startups with structured legal orientation on key issues such as governance, intellectual property, contract drafting, and regulatory compliance. Key activities included:

- April 2025: UniPd staff coordinated initial meetings between Prof. Sandei and selected startups (including Synargy and Algae Scope), helping define the scope and approach of the legal support service in alignment with startup needs.
- May 2025: In collaboration with Prof. Sandei and the UniPd communication team, a brochure was drafted to outline the objectives, topics, and modalities of the Legal Sanity Check. This material was designed for dissemination across the first and second acceleration cohorts.
- June 2025: The brochure was finalized and circulated to participating startups. UniPd staff supported its distribution and encouraged participation in the initiative, ensuring that legal advisory activities were well integrated with the broader startup coaching process.
- During this period, 3 startups benefited from legal coaching through 8 dedicated sessions held by Prof. Sandei. The support covered key legal aspects relevant to early-stage ventures, including the selection of the most suitable legal form for the startup, governance structures and co-founder/shareholder agreements, mechanisms for managing internal conflicts, intellectual property strategy and ownership, contract design (particularly in the context of joint development or licensing), regulatory obligations related to digital innovation (including AI and data protection), and legal risk assessment in view of attracting investors. The sessions

were tailored to each startup's level of maturity and sector, and were intended both as legal orientation and as practical risk mitigation guidance.

iNEST CCI
Work package CCI.4.3
Design of the Sustainable Stage
Responsabile: UNIPD

MACRO TIPOLOGIA delle ATTIVITA'

- Programma di valutazione Exit Readiness
- Simulazioni di due diligence pre-exit
- Workshop su strategie di exit

Programma di valutazione Exit Readiness: Benchmark – Practitioner report

[KPMG: The Road to Exit guide](#) [Exit Readiness | Deloitte UK](#)

[Untitled Document \(businessexitanalysis.com\)](#)
[Untitled Document \(huntercpa.com\)](#)

Agosto 2024 Update UNIPD – Spoke 5 1 Agosto 2024 Update UNIPD – Spoke 5 2

5.3. SPOKE 5 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Collaborative activities refer to participation of the working group to recurrent meetings organized at the Spoke level to update Spoke 5 members of the current activities as well as at the CCI level for coordination (scientific coordination) and in relation to scouting activities.

Number of Contacts and Meetings

- Catch-up meetings among scouting specialists: weekly meetings among UNIPD's scouting specialists; participation to 4 coordination meetings with the other spokes (May 2024 – October 2024): the meetings focused on sharing best practices for scouting and engaging top spin-offs, researchers, and outstanding students from each Spoke.
- Roughly 20 alignment meetings with spinoffs in the pre-acceleration phase.

Meetings for iNEST2 – iNEST2IMPACT: 4 (January 2025 – June 2025)

Dedicated to exploring future potential scenarios to ensure the startup/spin-off scouting programme becomes a sustainable and integrated activity within each Spoke.

During the January 2025–June 2025 period, UniPd staff contributed to the development and coordination of the **iNEST2impact** working group, aimed at defining long-term sustainability models for the iNEST ecosystem and supporting pathways for research valorisation beyond the standard acceleration funnel.

Key activities included:

- Participation in working group meetings, both online and in-person, to co-develop strategic directions for iNEST2impact.
- Delivery of a dedicated presentation on Venture Studio and Venture Building models, highlighting alternative frameworks for supporting research-based entrepreneurial initiatives, with a focus on identifying and developing “orphan projects” (promising but under-supported research outputs).
- Contribution to internal discussions on the selection and support mechanisms for early-stage ideas with low team readiness or limited business traction, proposing methods for de-risking and bridging them toward investor interest.
- Support in shaping a framework to identify non-linear innovation trajectories, in which high-potential research may follow different paths to impact (e.g. licensing, hybrid academic-industry models, venture co-founding).

These contributions aimed to enrich the CC1 strategy with new tools and methodologies to complement the accelerator and spin-off support already in place, fostering a more inclusive and durable innovation ecosystem.

5.4. SPOKE 5 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

Main results obtained:

- Improved understanding among professors and research fellows of the process of spin-off creation and its potential to translate research into market
- Active involvement of researchers in hands-on activities aimed at exploring how to transform research into innovative business ideas and initiate business development processes.
- Across the two rounds of the iNEST CC1 programme, the University of Padova contributed in both the pre-acceleration and acceleration phases, supporting the emergence and development of research-driven startups. During pre-acceleration:
 - UniPd activated a combination of scouting strategies—ranging from targeted outreach to spin-offs, StartCup participants, and patent holders, to open calls via institutional channels—resulting in over 30 candidate projects engaged across the two cycles. This led to the selection and admission of five startups into the acceleration programme (including STAT4VALUE, BBSof, Synargy, Ecobot, and Airfarm).
 - In the Acceleration stages, UniPd contributed by mentoring six startups across both rounds, providing structured 1:1 coaching, support on business modelling, fundraising, IP strategy, and market validation. Notably, startups such as Sindrel, Discovera, Synargy, and Algae Scope achieved top positions at Demo Days, demonstrating the effectiveness of UniPd's contribution in transforming high-potential research ideas into investor-ready

As part of the dissemination activities for the iNEST ecosystem, a poster titled “Cross-Cutting Activity 1: Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and spin-offs” was presented at an institutional event held at the Orto Botanico in Padua. The poster, authored by Stefano Biazzo, Pier Luigi Franceschini, and Alessio Cuccu, illustrated the objectives, methodology, and results of Cross-Cutting Activity 1 (CC1) under Spoke 5. It highlighted the three-phase approach adopted for startup scouting, pre-acceleration, acceleration, and fundraising, showcasing key outcomes from the first cycle and outlining the upcoming activities. The event provided an opportunity to present the strategic role of CC1 in fostering innovation and entrepreneurship across the iNEST consortium.

Legal Sanity Check was carried out with the support of Prof. Claudia Sandei (University of Padua) to help startups identify and address key legal issues. A total of 8 one-on-one sessions were conducted, supporting 3 startups from the acceleration program. Each startup received a tailored review covering corporate structure, shareholder agreements, intellectual property, contracts, and regulatory compliance. Practical recommendations were provided to strengthen their legal foundations and improve readiness for investment and growth opportunities.

On January 30th 2025, iNEST’s Open Innovation Day, organized under Cross-Cutting Activity 1 at the historic Palazzo del Bo (University of Padua), brought together 40 leading companies from the North-East to celebrate excellence in innovation and foster stronger synergies between industry and academia. The event highlighted iNEST’s commitment to exploring collaborative opportunities—such as co-development, startup acquisitions, and innovation-driven partnerships—between established firms and emerging startups. Moderated roundtables enabled business leaders to share firsthand experiences with open innovation strategies and to discuss potential avenues for technology transfer and cooperation with universities. Companies participating in the event have been awarded as

Innovation leaders based on specific innovation-related criteria (research carried out by University of Udine).

Further details can be found in the LinkedIn post by Massimo Gamberini:

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/gamberini_inest-open-innovation-day-premia-le-40-aziende-activity-7290776895229485057-lfax, and on the University of Trieste website:
<https://portale.units.it/en/news/open-innovation-day-inest-consortium>.

5.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

- **High Commitment of Senior Professors to Consulting Activities**

One of the challenges observed during the scouting and support process relates to the nature of some existing university spin-offs. While these initiatives are often successful within their domain and contribute positively to technology transfer and applied research, they typically adopt service-based models with limited scalability, making them less aligned with the investment criteria of most early-stage venture capitalists. In particular, they may lack the product focus and growth potential expected in high-impact startups. To address this, Scouting Specialists have reinforced their efforts in identifying and nurturing entrepreneurial ideas with scalable business models and strong market orientation, while continuing to support more traditional spin-offs through tailored advisory and mentoring activities.

Corrective Action:

- Increase support for Scouting Specialists during data collection and early engagement phases.
- Encourage senior professors/researchers to actively identify and delegate to a junior operational contact (e.g., postdoc, PhD student, research fellow) who can act as the main point of contact for follow-up and project development tasks.
- Promote delegation models observed in already structured groups, where clear internal coordination led to much more effective collaboration and smoother communication.

- **Lack of Support for Digital and Platform-Based Ideas**

A tendency was observed within the academic ecosystem to prioritize deep-tech ideas rooted in hard sciences, which are often seen as more aligned with the research expertise of universities. While these projects can be highly innovative and technically advanced, they do not always present the market readiness, scalability, or capital efficiency typically sought by early-stage investors. As a result, digital platform-based or business model-driven innovations — which may offer faster go-to-market opportunities and greater investor appeal — have sometimes received less attention or support. To address this, efforts are being made to broaden the evaluation framework, ensuring a more balanced consideration of both deep-tech and market-driven innovation. This includes refining selection criteria, raising awareness among evaluators, and showcasing a wider variety of successful startup models during mentoring and training activities.

- **Bias Towards Medical and Pharma Sectors**

The evaluation of proposals across diverse sectors has highlighted a recurring challenge: projects in domains such as health and clean-tech, which often address pressing societal needs, tend to stand out in cross-sector comparisons. While their relevance and potential impact are undeniable, this can make it difficult to fairly assess proposals from other sectors that may be equally innovative but less immediately linked to high-profile societal challenges. To ensure a more balanced and inclusive selection process, the introduction of thematic evaluation tracks or domain-specific assessment categories is being considered. This would allow each proposal to be evaluated within its appropriate context, encouraging diversity in the portfolio while maintaining high standards of quality and impact.

Pre-Acceleration – Task CC1.2

The primary challenge was related to conducting an effective selection of the most promising ideas. The difficulty stemmed from the significant size of the University of Padua (UniPD) and the extensive volume of research output and patents available, making it complex to identify and prioritize high-potential projects. To address this issue, a collaborative approach was adopted. Feedback and insights were sought from various teams and offices within UniPD and its broader network, including Third Mission, Technology Transfer, and Research Valorisation units. This multi-layered selection process aimed to ensure that a diverse evaluation framework would yield the best final choices of ideas, projects, and spin-offs for participation in the iNEST Acceleration Program.

Timelines and Commitment

The rigid and precise timelines imposed by the program posed a barrier for some promising startup ideas that required greater flexibility. Participants perceived this flexibility as necessary to better manage ongoing projects alongside their involvement in the iNEST program. For certain candidates, the lack of adaptable scheduling and the requirement for a fixed level of availability hindered their participation, preventing them from progressing beyond the pre-selection stage.

Status of Spin-offs and Startups

Another issue involved understanding the organizational structure and independence of startups. In some cases, despite an initial expression of interest, it became evident that the process might lead to unmet expectations for certain teams. This highlighted the need for clearer communication and alignment regarding the goals and requirements of the acceleration process.

Need for Support for Professors and Doctoral Students

Professors, researchers and doctoral students often expressed reluctance to engage with the economic and financial aspects of their projects. Addressing this concern could benefit from the development of targeted initiatives, such as workshops or networking events that connect patent holders with local businesses. These events would foster partnerships, providing practical guidance and facilitating the commercial application of research.

Additionally, observing the diverse levels of capability among teams in managing and capitalizing on patents suggests an opportunity to organize dedicated sessions for idea exchange. These could involve UniPD teams holding valuable patents, enabling them to share experiences, brainstorm innovative methods, and collaborate on strategies for enhancing the value and impact of their intellectual property.

5.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

As part of the ongoing efforts to strengthen innovation and technology valorization within the iNEST framework, the following actions are proposed. These initiatives will be developed in close collaboration with the University of Padua's Technology Transfer Office and other key ecosystem actors engaged in entrepreneurship and knowledge transfer.

- **Workshops and Brainstorming Sessions among Patent Holders (Cross-Departmental)**
Objective: Facilitate dialogue among patent holders from different departments of the University of Padua to encourage knowledge exchange and identify potential synergies between complementary technologies.
- **Workshops and Brainstorming Sessions between Patent Holders and Local Companies**

Objective: Building on previous initiatives — including the Open Innovation workshop held in Padua on January 31, 2025 — create direct connections between university patent holders and companies interested in the industrial exploitation of these technologies, with the goal of fostering collaborative development and commercialization partnerships

Next steps will include the following activities:

Potential Service Lines to Support “Orphan Projects”

Projects that have not yet gained access to acceleration programmes or failed to progress beyond pre-selection phases may still hold untapped potential. The following service lines, identified within the Spin-Off Venture Studio framework, can offer tailored pathways for their development:

- Technowatch / Technology Foresight**
A light-touch, low-barrier entry point to monitor emerging trends and position “orphan” ideas within future technological landscapes. Useful for refining project relevance and timing.
- Academy – Learning & Knowledge Provider**
A structured opportunity for teams to strengthen entrepreneurial, business, or sector-specific skills, often lacking in early-stage or research-driven initiatives. Could serve as a bridge towards future readiness.
- Joint Research Programs**
For promising but immature or complex ideas, collaborative research projects can provide a nurturing environment to refine concepts, generate evidence, and build partnerships — particularly with departments aligned to the project topic.
- Start-up Scouting, Selection & Custom Matching**
Offers the chance to reframe and reposition “orphan” projects by matching them with external needs (e.g. investors, corporate partners, or market niches) through personalised scouting and strategic alignment activities.

All “orphan projects” identified within Spoke 5 were analyzed based on two key dimensions:

(1) **the completeness of the team** leading the idea/startup/spinoff, and

(2) **the maturity and clarity of the idea**, especially in terms of its ability to address a concrete, verifiable problem or respond to a clearly identified need.

This assessment aimed to better understand the potential of each project and to define tailored support actions where possible.

Main challenges

The Challenge Ahead: Advancing Toward Project Viability

Following two successful testing and implementation rounds of Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration, the forthcoming stage in development will involve addressing a critical challenge: ensuring its long-term self-sustainability.

Scouting specialists will be tasked with identifying and applying effective, original, and scalable methodologies to sustain and expand the project's impact.

The objective is to continue facilitating the transition from academic research to the innovation ecosystem by:

- Providing targeted support services and tailored advisory activities for researchers, inventors, and academic spin-off initiatives.
- Fostering meaningful connections within and beyond academia,
- Promoting awareness and engagement across the research community,
- Supporting the identification, development, and maturation of the most promising spin-off initiatives generated within the SPOKE,
- Enabling access to funding opportunities and paving the way for successful market scalability.

This phase could represent not only a continuation of prior efforts but a decisive step toward achieving structural and financial sustainability.

6. SPOKE 6 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

Spoke 6 research focuses on enabling businesses in tourism, culture, and creative sectors to transform research into practical outcomes via prototypes, experiments, and innovations. Its incubation and acceleration projects support entrepreneurial ideas in these fields, guided by four key Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT 1 - New Digital Technologies**

These lines promote the development of innovative projects that combine knowledge of the tourism and cultural domain with the adoption of new digital technologies. These include artificial intelligence, blockchain and NFT, IoT and mobile sensing, virtual and augmented reality, which will serve as a reference for projects to be implemented in the following macro-environments;

- **RT 2 - Data analysis**

These converge on the analysis of big data in tourism and culture from heterogeneous sources. The aim is thus to develop tools to support public policies and more sustainable destination management & marketing strategies. The lines of research may take the form of projects to be implemented in different fields;

- **RT 3 - Sustainable business models**

RT3 research lines aim at transforming the business models of tourism, cultural and creative enterprises, organisations and ecosystems into sustainable ones.

- **RT 4 - New narratives and communication strategies**

The RT4 research lines aim to develop new narrative tools to overcome the stereotypes of tourist destinations and to reconfigure communication in terms of inclusiveness and sustainability.

Spoke 6, led by Ca' Foscari University with partners from the Universities of Verona, Trento, and Bolzano, is establishing a robust tourism ecosystem that integrates culture, creativity, and advanced digital and data analysis technologies. It focuses on four key research areas to explore the intricate connections within the tourism sector, fostering innovation, sustainability, and transformative practices.

Within the framework of the iNEST project, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 6 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs. Furthermore, it assumes a fundamental role in coordinating and stimulating the achievement of project objectives, promoting the exploration of new solutions and pathways through continuous listening and exchange. This approach creates a vital communication system essential for fostering growth and innovation across the entire ecosystem.

6.1. SPOKE 6 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Cross-Cutting Activity 1 aims to foster the creation and selection of innovative ideas generated by the scientific community of its Spokes, leveraging internal and external actors in guiding them towards their transformation into research-driven start-ups and spin-offs.

Within this activity, Spoke 6 objectives were to first conduct in-Spoke dissemination and selection of promising ideas and then to actively contribute to the following project phases and supporting the selected startups. Their founders took part in a comprehensive acceleration programme, including six workshops and two pitch clinics, designed to enhance their entrepreneurial skills, to help them develop robust business models and to prepare them to scale their ventures.

At the same time Spoke 6 aimed to contribute to public communication efforts, highlighting key milestones of the programme. Particular emphasis was placed on showcasing the mission, vision and innovative aspects of the start-ups, sharing their progress and achievements with a wider audience.

The main contributor to the CC1 for Spoke 6 was the scouting specialist, whose individual goals included to ensure effective communication between local / sector-specific actors and the CC1 centralised management, bringing together diverse expertise and resources for successful operations and team growth.

Finally, Spoke 6 aimed to support the reflection and conceptualisation on potential strategies for the continuation of iNEST CC1 beyond its PNRR funded phase.

6.2. SPOKE 6 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem. Responsible: UNIVE - Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies. Responsible: UNIUD - Duration: months 9-40
- **CC1.3: Acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem. Responsible: UNIVR - Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase. Responsible: UNIVR - Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCRUM program. The objective of this phase is to bring

the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model. Responsible: UNIVR -
Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 6

Background/State of the Art: a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: the Acceleration program was structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blended theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), were also part of the program. The 2nd cycle acceleration program saw the implementation of a methodological curvature, based on feedback received in the 1st cycle. The main improvements were:

- the introduction of a strategic plan document (as a backbone of the program and final output to be produced by the startups)
- the strengthening of the coaching system by assigning two coaches to each team (1 "operative" coach and 1 "field expert" coach)
- the use of a program management platform (Accelerator App).

In the following, the 2nd cycle programme is detailed:

- 2nd cycle:
 - Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: "Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan".
 - Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: "Problem, current solutions, and proposition".
 - Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: "Market and competition".
 - Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca' Foscari): "Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model".
 - Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav).
 - Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: "Action plan & eco-fin plan".
 - Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: "Eco-fin plan & funding".
 - Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops were based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program was peer learning: participants learn from one another

by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development. Every start-up team was assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who helped them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches followed start-up teams during the workshops and organized one-on-one coaching sessions.

During the semester, the Spoke 6 Scouting Specialist was actively involved in all stages of the process and remained available throughout. In particular, Viviana Carlet provided dedicated support and mentoring to two start-ups: **EcoBot** and **OptiLink**. Viviana also participated in regular meeting with the Acceleration management team and the coaches team, which were held every two weeks and in which she provided updates on the two assigned startups.

OptiLink

Senior Coach: Luca Pavan

Focus: Automatic transcription and medical data management

Support: idea definition, communication, pitch and narrative

The OptiLink project has been a complex but educational journey. The project was supported during the second iNEST CCI acceleration cycle by the senior coach Luca Pavan. The idea was born with the aim of simplifying bureaucratic processes and improving clinical data management through an AI-based digital assistant, with a particular focus on automatic transcription of visits and support for early diagnosis. The team, made up of very young students with an enthusiastic approach, showed great energy, listening skills and a willingness to learn, but had to face a steeper learning curve than other groups. In particular, strengths and weaknesses emerged:

- **Strengths:** enthusiasm, proactivity, openness to discussion and tangible growth in pitch presentation and ability to communicate the value of the project.
- **Critical issues:** the project still appeared immature, with frequent changes in strategy and product definition; the team's limited entrepreneurial skills slowed down the structuring of the business model and market planning. Significant issues remain unresolved, such as regulatory compliance in the healthcare sector, the definition of competitive positioning and the solidity of technological and commercial scalability.

Despite these difficulties, OptiLink benefited from the acceleration programme, learning to better structure its proposals, strengthen narrative clarity and enhance teamwork. The project is likely to require further incubation and mentoring cycles to reach sufficient maturity to compete in the market, but the experience represented a fundamental step in the team's entrepreneurial and professional growth.

EcoBot

Senior Coach: Valter Carturo

Focus: AI for waste sorting

Support: strategy, storytelling and presentation development

The EcoBot project, which was followed during the second acceleration cycle of iNEST CCI by the senior coach Valter Carturo, showed significant progress, especially in terms of structuring the business idea and the personal growth of its founder.

Despite a hesitant start and some initial uncertainties related to defining the problem and the value proposition, the team demonstrated the ability to listen, openness to discussion, and a willingness to improve. During the programme, thanks to the constant support of coach Valter Carturo and the

continuous revision of the strategic plan, EcoBot managed to: clarify the target audience, improve the pitch narrative, and define more concretely the distinctive element of the solution, based on an intelligent robotic system for waste sorting, integrated with AI technologies.

The project stands out for its potential environmental impact and innovative drive in the automation of waste management, in a sector that is still largely undigitised. However, some residual critical issues have emerged, in particular: the actual technological positioning of the device within the industrial supply chain; the need to validate the concept in real environments (pilot tests); the need to strengthen the strategic and commercial component for effective market entry.

Overall, EcoBot has demonstrated its ability to seize the opportunities offered by the acceleration programme, growing in technical, relational and design terms. The project has a solid technical foundation and, with the right industrial and consulting support, could represent an interesting proposition in the field of green tech and the circular economy.

Viviana Carlet also remained in contact with the two projects supported by Spoke 6 that passed the selection process: Fenix Ceramics and Algae Scope.

The 2nd cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Venezia on June 26, 2025, featuring an external jury of investors and other stakeholders of the iNEST innovation ecosystem (CDP Venture Partners, Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Invitalia, MITO Technology, Obloo Ventures, VeniSIA). Algae Scope was awarded 2nd place while **EcoBot** received a special mention for the commitment shown throughout the programme and for the progress made.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3** all the activities of the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program are completed.

6.3. SPOKE 6 CC1 DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Spoke 6 continued to promote CC1-related updates and events, which were widely disseminated through a number of channels. These included news articles published on the iNEST, Spoke 6 and UNIVE websites, social media posts on LinkedIn and Facebook. All promotional activities were carried out in collaboration with and coordinated by CESA. The visibility of the accelerated startups, as in the 1st cycle, was further enhanced by a series of short video interviews carried out by the CC1 communication team and published on YouTube.

During the reporting period the scouting specialist maintained active links with relevant Spoke and ecosystem actors - in particular inside Ca' Foscari with: CLab, PInK (Promozione dell'Innovazione e del Know-how) (the technology transfer and valorisation office), Student Associations - and was engaged in the following collaborative activities:

- weekly participation in the AIKU research centre
- collaboration on the iNEST Young Researchers call for proposals
- support for iNEST CC3 residential activities
- participation to iNEST2 co-design meetings.

6.4. SPOKE 6 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

After an initial year dedicated to launching and structuring the scouting system, the period between January and June 2025 marked a phase of consolidation, optimisation and progressive maturation of

the entire CCI process. The experience gained has made it possible to refine selection strategies and evaluation criteria, better calibrate work tools and strengthen support pathways.

A decisive factor was the strengthening of collaboration between scouting specialists, Spoke representatives and institutional partners, facilitated by more direct, structured and transparent communication. This continuous and constructive exchange has enabled more effective project management, improving the quality of applications, the efficiency of acceleration pathways and the alignment between research, business and the local area.

The critical issues that emerged in the first cycle were addressed in a systematic manner, transforming them into opportunities for improvement that led to more solid results and greater cohesion between the various components of the iNEST ecosystem.

From the second round of scouting, two ideas selected by Ca' Foscari's spoke 6 were selected for the acceleration phase: Fenix Ceramics and Algae Scope.

Fenix Ceramics is an innovative start-up that aims to revolutionise the ceramic materials sector through the use of sustainable technologies and circular production processes. The project focuses on recovering waste from incinerators and transforming it into new ceramic materials with low environmental impact, suitable for applications in design, construction and street furniture. The goal is to create a product that combines aesthetics, functionality and sustainability, helping to reduce raw material consumption and emissions associated with traditional ceramic production.

Algae Scope is an entrepreneurial project created to develop solutions based on the cultivation and processing of macroalgae as a tool for carbon capture, bioproduct production and environmental regeneration. The team intends to develop facilities and technologies for algae cultivation in controlled environments, with the aim of creating an innovative and sustainable supply chain for applications in sectors such as cosmetics, agriculture, nutraceuticals and biodegradable materials. The vision is to integrate scientific research and environmental impact, promoting a circular and low-impact production model.

Moreover, the Scouting Specialist Viviana Carlet was involved in the coaching of two of the selected teams, namely EcoBot and OptiLink, that both completed the acceleration path successfully and were admitted to the Demo Day.

Of the abovementioned teams: Algae Scope resulted among the top 3 teams awarded at the 2nd Demo Day (Venice, June 26th) and, in the same event, EcoBot was publicly recognised for its commitment and progress. These results testify the improved Spoke 6 contribution to both the Pre-acceleration (selecting Algae Scope) and the Acceleration phases (coaching EcoBot).

The main results achieved during the semester: strengthening of internal skills within the scouting system, greater quality and variety of project ideas collected, successful engagement of the academic and research community, refinement of the acceleration methodologies, increasing consistency and quality of the support provided to start-ups, culminating in more impactful results in the second round.

6.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

As in the 1st cycle, cultural and tourism projects, while rich and innovative, often lacked the entrepreneurial skills to succeed in a market-driven environment and did not find their way into the Acceleration program. Beyond requiring additional time and tailored support, many of these initiatives often require alternative business models that are better suited to their nature.

Innovative ideas in the humanities, characterised by a strong cultural and inclusive impact, had in scalability and long-term economic sustainability their main critical weaknesses. These limitations affect the projects' attractiveness to traditional investors and highlight the need for alternative funding strategies and support systems tailored to the unique characteristics of cultural and humanities-focused initiatives.

No new relevant problems arose during 2025.

6.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

For the Spoke 6 specific research areas the key challenges remain:

- Ongoing support and ecosystem building: creating a supportive environment to nurture ideas and encourage humanistic entrepreneurship. This includes creating a network that supports innovation and bridges the gap between creative concepts and market implementation.
- Experimenting with hybrid business models: developing innovative business models that combine profitability with cultural and social impact. These models aim to transcend traditional start-up dynamics, ensuring market relevance while addressing societal and cultural needs.
- Integrating culture, entrepreneurship and innovation: strengthening the synergy between these fields to foster sustainable initiatives. By aligning cultural resources with entrepreneurial strategies and technological advances, the aim is to respond effectively to the evolving needs of communities.
- Building bridges between research and management: creating links between technical and scientific research, cultural ideas and management expertise. These aspects are present within the university but rarely intersect, both physically (as they are often located in different spaces) and conceptually (lack of platforms for open dialogue and interaction). Initiatives such as the collaboration with the IUAV - a university dedicated to artistic creation - are particularly valuable. Such partnerships activate diverse processes, stimulate collaborative creation and encourage the sharing and distribution of competences.

Considering the overall cross-cutting activity 1, next steps and challenges are: completing the implementation of the Fundraising phase, attracting potential investors, establishing a long-standing relationship between the partners and the external stakeholders that were involved in the project and finding potential win-win solutions for the continuation of the CC1 initiative.

References

We report here the list of the links to the webpages relevant to Spoke 6 and in particular to Cross-Cutting Activity 1:

- [Spoke 6 website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the iNEST website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the Spoke 6 website](#)
- [Results of the 2nd cycle of CC1 \(page on the iNEST website\)](#)
- [List of news concerning CC1 on the iNEST website](#)

7. SPOKE 7 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 7 address current issues in the sector of smart agri-food.

These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- RT1 - Business models for a sustainable agri-food
- RT2 - Process and product innovation for a sustainable agri-food
- RT3 - Circular economy
- RT4 - Logistics, supply chain and vertical coordination.

In this scientific context, Cross-Cutting Activity 1 plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 7 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

7.1. SPOKE 7 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Scouting and Support for University Entrepreneurial Projects

The Spoke 7 Team (Valter Carturo, Gianni Tortella e Franco Bocchini) has initiated a systematic scouting effort for technology projects generated within the University, with the aim of:

- identifying ideas with entrepreneurial potential,
- supporting faculty, researchers, and potential founders in transforming technological ideas into entrepreneurial projects.

Results Achieved

- Approximately ten innovative projects were identified and supported,
- of these, two were selected to access the acceleration program provided by the iNEST program: BESAFE and Qualyco.

7.2. SPOKE 7 CCI TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CCI Tasks in the reporting period Jan. 1st - June 30th 2025:

- **CCI.3: Acceleration**
 - Sub Task CCI.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CCI.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CCI.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, sprint program and Demo Day. The objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.

Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 7

Mentoring and Coaching

The Team also provided mentoring and coaching to projects from the University of Verona and beyond, supporting them during the critical phases of the iNEST process, with particular attention to:

- Business model definition,
- Technology validation,
- Initial market and industrial stakeholder engagement.

In particular Valter Carturo provided individualised support to two of the teams accelerated in the 2nd cycle, being the senior coach for: AIRFARM and EcoBot. Both teams evolved during the program and were admitted to the Demo Day (Venice, June 26th 2025), where EcoBot was also awarded a special mention for its commitment and significant progress. As a coach, Valter Carturo participated in regular meetings with the Acceleration management team and the other coaches, providing updates on the startups every two weeks and giving feedback and suggestions for the refinement of the program structure and offer.

In addition, Marco Cristani was an active member of the Acceleration management team and contributed also to the program workshops with a presentation titled "AI Unleashed! A 360° view for startup innovators" (Venice, workshop 4, March 15th 2025).

Participation in the Project Recovery Task Force

Members of the Spoke actively participate in a cross-functional task force with the dual objective of:

- Recovering and reactivating technology projects initially analyzed but not pursued,
- Consolidating a structured technology transfer system at the University level, aimed at creating an environment conducive to the creation and growth of innovative companies

Methodological Approach

The Team's activities were conducted using a socio-technical approach based on:

- systemic analysis of the university ecosystem,
- listening to the needs of researchers and potential entrepreneurs,
- defining operational tools and organizational models for the transition from research to business,
- building connections with the industrial world through matching activities, workshops, and face-to-face meetings.

7.3. SPOKE 7 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

In addition to taking part in the *Demo Day* held in Venice on 26 June 2025, the Team facilitated connections between start-up founders and the ecosystem of business angels and investment funds.

7.4. SPOKE 7 CCI MAIN RESULTS

Spoke 7's work has achieved the following objectives:

- spreading a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation within the University of Verona,
- encouraging the creation of start-ups and open innovation initiatives,

· contributing to the University's transformation into a key player in the country's industrial development.

The long-term goal is to create a sustainable ecosystem in which the University becomes an active driver for the generation of deep-tech start-ups capable of significantly contributing to the growth of Italian and European industry.

7.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The experience gained confirms the importance of an integrated and multidisciplinary approach, capable of mediating between scientific research and industrial development, facilitating the translation of technological potential into economic and social impact.

Spoke 7's contribution is part of a strategic path aimed at strengthening the University's role as a natural incubator of innovation and entrepreneurial future.

8. SPOKE 8 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 8 address current issues in the sectors of maritime, marine and inland water technologies: towards the digital twin of the Upper Adriatic. These are supported and enhanced by five Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1** Biology of hydrosphere ecosystems
- **RT2** Physical-chemical risks and impacts on the hydrosphere
- **RT3** Sustainable waterway mobility
- **RT4** Land-sea integrated maritime and spatial Planning
- **RT5** North Adriatic Digital twin

In this scientific context, the **Cross-Cutting Activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of the Spoke 8 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

8.1. SPOKE 8 CCI OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, the overarching goal of the CCI is to foster the generation and selection of innovative ideas emerging from the scientific activities of Spoke 8, with the ultimate aim of transforming these ideas into research-based start-ups and spin-offs. To achieve this, CCI is structured into four distinct phases: planning and validation of activities, pre-acceleration, acceleration, fundraising.

The first phase focuses on the planning and validation of activities, involving university personnel and industry technical personnel dedicated to supporting the initiatives as outlined by the CCI Committee.

Pre-acceleration and scouting activities were intended to collect entrepreneurial ideas, select them and provide the most promising ones with the basic tools for the development and flourishing of their innovative potential, thus allowing them to turn into start-ups and spin-offs.

The acceleration phase aimed to assist these teams in developing robust business models. To this end, the founders joined an Acceleration Program comprising six workshops and two pitch clinics, designed to refine their entrepreneurial skills and prepare them for scaling their ventures.

The fundraising phase represents a crucial moment for any startup, as it provides the financial resources needed to develop the product, expand the team, and access the market. Fundraising also allows the business model to be validated, increasing the company's credibility in the eyes of customers and partners. Successfully navigating this phase means laying the foundation for sustainable and long-term growth.

The start-ups selected in the second cycle of CCI entered the Acceleration Program in January 2025. It consisted of six workshops and two pitch clinics aimed at strengthening their entrepreneurial skills and preparing them to scale their ventures. This third phase culminated in the Demo Day, held on 26 June 2025 in Venice. Both Spoke 8-related start-up projects, OptiLink and SIPEOM, successfully reached this stage and presented their initiatives during the event, with SIPEOM earning third place. In parallel, the Fundraising phase was launched with the goal of supporting the most promising start-ups in transitioning into scale-ups. This phase includes dedicated training cycles delivered by expert consultants and involves participants from both the first and second acceleration cohorts. Within this framework, Spoke 8 is committed to assisting investment-ready scale-ups in meeting their

financial needs by developing a fundraising network, identifying and engaging potential investors - including venture capital funds and business angels - and providing guidance in negotiating and structuring investment deals.

8.2. SPOKE 8 CC1 TASKS AND ONGOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- CC1.2: Pre-acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- **CC1.3: Acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. The objective of this

phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 15-32

- **CC1.4: Fundraising**

- Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management. The task involves developing a fundraising network.

Responsible: UNITS

Duration: months 15–40

- Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage to support investment-ready scaleups fulfilling their financial needs.

Responsible: UNITS

Duration: months 21–34

- Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage.

Responsible: UNIPD

Duration: months 23–40

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 8

Background/State of the Art: Sub-task CC1.3.1 and Sub-task CC1.3.2 have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external) are also part of the program. While the acceleration phase for the start-ups involved in the first cycle ended up with the Demo Day in October 2024, the start-ups selected for the second cycle started this phase in January 2025. The detailed program follows.

- Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.
- Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
- Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
- Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
- Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (IUAV).

- Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
- Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
- Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning - participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development.

Every start-up team was assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who helped the teams to apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches followed start-up teams during the workshops and also organized one-on-one coaching sessions. The AcceleratorApp software has been used for the organization and management of this cycle of the activity.

The 2nd cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Venice on June 26, 2025. The Spoke8 related start-up SIPEOM was awarded third place.

Focus on Task CC1.4: Fundraising

As for **CC1.4 Fundraising activities**, Spoke 8 has followed the detailed plan of action presented in the last report, addressed to startups participating in the acceleration program of both the first and the second cycle.

Background/state of the art: since June 2024, the representatives of Spoke 8 from UniTS and PoloAA started to plan the Fundraising initiatives that started in 2025. The composite program has been performed in different stages and covered full-fledged topics on financial aspects concerning the startup funding. The fundraising phase aims at leading successful start-ups to become scaleups. The Spoke 8, in this phase, is supporting early stage startups in getting familiar with terminology and dynamics for startup funding and is helping the investment-ready scaleups to fulfil their financial needs, by developing a fundraising network, identifying and approaching potential investors including VC/BA and helping in negotiating/structuring investment deals.

Methodology: The start-ups emerging from the iNEST acceleration program are being supported by specialists and guided towards adopting the most effective approaches to fundraising. Around June, 30th 2025, Spoke 8 has finalized all the public procedures for turning into action the fundraising program and has concluded some of them, putting in place the first concrete actions in support to the startups. The details for each foreseen action are explained as follows.

1. **The Vocabulary of Credit:** public procedure closed with Heritage srl on May 21st 2025.

This training started on **May 25th** with a phygital session from 9.00 to 13.00, where the trainer was in presence at Innovators Community Lab in via Fabio Severo 40, Trieste.

Main topics addressed in this session for startups investment were:

Personal Financial Management and Startup Readiness

Importance of building an emergency fund (not to be invested):

Equal to 3 months of expenses for employees

Equal to 6 months for freelancers/self-employed (e.g., startup founders)

Recommended tools to save money:

Deposit account

Second current account
Savings book
Digital piggy banks or round-up features in banking apps
Expense tracking is essential to understand real financial needs
Main goal: money management should bring peace of mind, not stress

Financial Risks and Personal Strategy

Subjective risks: inability to save, lack of a financial strategy, giving up due to frustration
It is essential to set priorities and follow a realistic plan
The emergency fund acts as a "parachute" - especially important when entering entrepreneurship

Italian Economic Context

Italy's public debt has surpassed €3 trillion, equivalent to 135.3% of GDP
Each newborn carries a virtual debt of €49,000
Consequences for citizens: strain on healthcare, pensions, public services, and higher tax pressure

Implications for Startups

Having an emergency fund is crucial before launching a startup to handle personal and professional uncertainties
The lack of financial independence among young people creates obstacles in accessing:
Initial capital
Bank loans
Public funding or support programs
It is vital to assess your financial capacity and prepare before starting a business

At this session we had 9 startupper from 7 startups (2 of the 1st cycle and 5 from the 2nd cycle, 4 online and 5 in presence).

The second and third sessions were held online.

The second session had this programme:

June 12, 2025 | 9:30 AM – 18:00

- Importance of knowing financing instruments for startups
- Essential Glossary: capital, debt, and equity
- Differences between debt financing and equity financing
- Concepts of risk and return
 - Peculiarities of startups
 - Financing a new business unit
- Healthy debt makes the company grow
- Relationship between debt and profitability
- When not to ask the bank for money: hint at over-indebtedness
- Shareholders' capital
- Startup valuation
- How a startup is valued
- Valuation multiples and key metrics
- Common validation errors
- ANGEL INVESTORS:
 - EBAN (European Business Angel Network)

- MIND THE BRIDGE (organization that facilitates matching supply and demand)
- AngelList
- CONFINDUSTRIA:
 - Innovation Enterprise Award
 - CONNEXT startup program
 - THE STARTUP CLUB
 - TALENTIS roadmaps for selection
 - WOMEN IN STEM
- IT'S CAMPUS
- VENTURE CAPITAL: difference between venture capital and private equity
 - Objective of VC / Objectives of PE
 - VC and PE equity stake
 - Venture Capital Report 2024
 - CDP VENTURE CAPITAL
 - Smart & Start
- How to prepare an effective pitch
- Necessary documents
- Practical advice
- CROWDFUNDING
 - Regulations, subjects, method, and timings.
 - Most well-known platforms
 - KICKSTARTER
 - INDIEGOGO
 - GOFUNDME
 - CROWDFOUNDER
 - MAMACROWD
 - SEEDRS
 - CROWDCUBE
 - Practical tips for a successful campaign
- WHAT ARE PUBLIC FUNDING:
 - SUBSIDIZED INTEREST RATE
 - NON-REPAYABLE GRANT
- WHERE TO FIND THEM:
 - Ministry of Interior:
 - New businesses at zero interest
 - Smart & Start
 - Ministry of Business and Made in Italy:
 - Tax deductions up to 65% for those investing in Innovative Startups
 - Tax credit for incubators and accelerators
 - Capital gain exemption for a minimum participation of at least three years
 - Simplified access to the SME Guarantee Fund up to 80%
 - Voucher 3l
 - Fail fast and simplified rapid liquidation procedures in case of failure
 - MICROCREDIT
 - Inail Startup Call
 - EUROPEAN FUNDS: analysis of the EU Funding & Tenders portal
 - "DIGITAL EUROPE 2021-2027" €8.1 BILLION
 - Horizon Europe
 - InvestEU
 - Creative Europe Media

- EU4Health
 - EUROPEAN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT FUND:
 - RESTO AL SUD CALL
- NON-REPAYABLE GRANTS
 - CDP Smart Money
 - SME CAPITALIZATION FUND
- REPORTING

At the second meeting nobody was present, so the session was recorded and sent to all the startups of both cycles.

The third session had this programme:

June 13, 2025 | 9:30 AM – 13.00

- **How banks evaluate individuals:** what is credit rating and how it affects the interest rate on borrowed money
- **Bank financial instruments:**
 - Credit assessment
 - Bank advances
 - “Hot money” credit
 - Mortgages
 - Subsidized loans
 - Agricultural credit
 - Construction credit
 - Leasing
 - Factoring
- **Financial sustainability analysis**
- **Debt guarantees:**
 - Real guarantees (e.g. collateral)
 - Personal guarantees
 - Collective guarantees
- **Financing long-term investments**
- **Safe access to credit:**
 - How to evaluate credit offers
 - How to avoid scams and unfair practices
- **Protection tools and support:**
 - Role of credit intermediaries
 - Differences between banks, finance companies, and credit brokers
 - How to choose a reliable intermediary
- **Key parameters for credit offers:**
 - Interest rates
 - Fees
 - Terms and conditions
 - Use of online comparison platforms
- **How and where to invest money:**
 - The importance of the time horizon
 - Understanding risk and return
 - Matching investment choices with personal goals

- **Choosing financial intermediaries:**
 - Banks, financial advisors, online platforms
 - How to verify if they are authorized and trustworthy
 - Understanding the cost of services and products
- **Key questions before making an investment:**
 - What am I investing for?
 - How long can I keep my money invested?
 - How much risk can I tolerate?
- **Tools for evaluating offers:**
 - Use of online comparison tools and official sources
 - Reading product information documents (KIDs, prospectuses, etc.)
 - Understanding fees, expected returns, and potential risks

At this last meeting we had 2 startupper online from 2 startups of the second cycle.

All the sessions have been recorded and sent to all the startupper together with the training material. The startupper had also the opportunity to have one-to-one meetings with the trainer for individual analysis and one startupper of the first cycle asked for it.

2. **Meetings with Banks.** Public procedure closed with Strategia & Controllo srl on April 30th 2025.

This training started on with a phygital session on **May 24th** from 14:00 to 18:00, where the trainer was in presence at Innovators Community Lab in via Fabio Severo 40, Trieste, but there was only online participation from 1 startupper of the first cycle, that had the chance to discuss his startup situation in a one-to-one meeting with a banking consultant.

The second meeting was on Friday, **June 27** from 9:00 AM to 6:00 PM, at Università Ca' Foscari Venezia, Campus San Giobbe, aula 6A, Fondamenta S. Giobbe 873, Venezia. The program's topics were:

- 9:00 AM - 10:45 AM: Presentation of the day - Tips and Tricks with the banking sector by Strategia&Controllo srl
- 10:45 AM - 11:00 AM: Coffee break
- 11:00 AM - 1:00 PM: Reward Crowdfunding with testimony from a funded startup by Ginger Crowdfunding
- 1:00 PM - 2:00 PM: Lunch break
- 2:00 PM - 3:00 PM: Equity Crowdfunding as blending finance by Cosmos Finance
- 3:00 PM - 4:00 PM: The role of Confidi for access to credit by Fidimpresa FriulVeneto
- 4:00 PM - 4:15 PM: Coffee break
- 4:15 PM - 6:00 PM: Tools to support startups by CiviBank, Banca di Cividale SpA

At this meeting we had 6 startupper from 3 startups (1 of the first cycle and 2 from the second one), two of them in presence and the others online.

The last 2 meetings (in July, after the end date of this report) were only online, due to the absence of in presence subscriptions. The programme was the following:

For **July 2nd**:

- 9:00 – 9:15 Introduction to the morning Strategy & Control srl
- 9:15 – 11:00 Tools and initiatives to support startups and SMEs Cassa Centrale Banca
- 11:00 – 11:15 Coffee break

- 11:15 – 13:00 Tools and initiatives to support startups and SMEs Banca Popolare di Sondrio Cross Program

For **July 9th**:

- 9:00 AM - 9:10 AM: Introduction to the day by Strategia&Controllo srl.
- 9:10 AM - 10:00 AM: Tools and guarantees for startups and SMEs by BCC Venezia Giulia.
- 10:00 AM - 11:00 AM: Startup and new enterprise financing, banking Venture Capital solutions by Intesa San Paolo.
- 11:00 AM - 11:15 AM: Coffee break.
- 11:15 AM - 1:00 PM: Crowdfunding for startups and SMEs by Ginger.
- 1:00 PM - 2:00 PM: Lunch break.
- 2:00 PM - 3:00 PM: Obtaining financial resources to develop and scale one's business by Le Village by CA.
- 3:00 PM - 4:00 PM: Tools and guarantees for startups and SMEs by Banca 360 Credito Cooperativo.
- 4:00 PM - 4:15 PM: Coffee break.
- 4:15 PM - 5:30 PM: Guarantees to facilitate access to credit for startups and SMEs by Confidi Venezia Giulia.
- 5:30 PM - 6:00 PM: Conclusions and Q&A by Strategia&Controllo srl.

Also in this case the startupper had the opportunity to have 1 to 1 meeting with credit institutions but until now no one has requested this service.

3. **Meetings with Enterprises**: public procedure started in May 2025 and has been closed on around 30th July 2025. Start-ups will have the opportunity to present their ideas through structured "speed-dating" activities, fostering direct interaction with potential industry partners.
4. Public procedure closed with Fermo Tech S.C.aR.L. on June 20th for a **service agreement** for the strategic design and execution of **events** aimed at enhancing the innovation ecosystem within the "iNEST – Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem" project. This project is funded by the European Union through NextGenerationEU and is part of Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR). The core of the service involves the complete design, execution, organization, and management of two events. These events are primarily categorized as "Management consulting services" (CPV 80110000-8), with secondary activities falling under "Event organization services" (CPV 79952000-2). The service is considered to be of a predominantly intellectual nature, focusing on creative design, strategic planning, methodological coordination, and content enhancement to produce highly specialized events.

Two national and interregional events (to be realized in Trieste) are planned at the conclusion of the two acceleration cycles (2023-2024 and 2024-2025) to present the results.

Event N. 1 Details: This will be a national event realized in Trieste involving specialized stakeholders in the marine and maritime innovation and entrepreneurial training sectors.

Specific Objectives: Promote dialogue among businesses, institutions, research bodies, and creatives; offer an immersive and professional experience with national/international speakers; include workshops, round tables, and pitch sessions.

Required Activities: Event ideation and creative format (title, storytelling, graphics, line-up); identification, involvement, and payment of speakers, jurors, moderators, and specialized actors (including travel, food, and lodging expenses); selection and management of physical or digital location (including rent, security, cleaning costs); technical management of audio/video/lights/streaming; organizational secretariat and reception; guest schedule, jury

coordination, translations, and/or press area; communication and promotion (media kit, social media, press); creation of a final report with impact indicators; catering and coffee breaks.

Challenge: After presentations, a collective challenge will be launched based on the three-year research results of Spoke 8, focusing on five thematic research areas: Biology of marine ecosystems, Innovation in managing physical and chemical risks and their impact on the hydrosphere, Innovation in sustainable coastal transport, Integrated land-sea maritime and spatial planning, and Development of a Digital Twin of the Upper Adriatic. Mixed groups of CCI sea/water startups and startups/spin-offs from the south that passed self-entrepreneurship tests will work on these themes in a final hackathon, structured like a Google Design Sprint, to rapidly generate prototypes, innovative ideas, and concrete solutions.

Duration: From 10:00 AM on October 13th to 4:00 PM on October 14th.

Event N. 2 Details: This will be an interregional event realized in Trieste to promote the overall iNEST results achieved in Friuli-Venezia Giulia (FVG) and other North-East regions.

Specific Objectives: Activate connections among research entities and businesses in the North-East; share good business practices and territorial strategies; stimulate co-design or internationalization opportunities; reflect on the future of the ecosystem.

Required Activities: Definition of event format and target; identification and involvement of representative companies (including potential coverage of travel, food, and lodging expenses for invited guests); planning and logistical execution (venue, catering, informational materials); facilitation activities (speed meetings, cluster sessions, keynote); technical support and organizational secretariat; local and national promotion; drafting of a summary of results and participant follow-up.

Duration: From 4:30 PM to 10:30 PM on October 14th, 2025, with a light dinner at 8:00 PM.

5. Public procedure started in May 2025 for a **service** regarding the creation of **IT solutions** configurable in modular components of a web-app platform with a so called ROOM 2 – High Potential Showroom and Venture Capitalist Platform with the following characteristics:

Profiling For the section with the INEST thematic areas, where the following will be provided:

- Access with assessment of the degree of self-entrepreneurship (create a profiling table with different services)
- TEST with questions to assess the degree of self-entrepreneurship, which gives access to sections a) and b):

a) *Innovation matching consultancy*

Standard presentation form (project ideas and startups)

- Public dashboard with startup/spinoff showcase
- Book a pitch and assess your skills

b) *Development and Training*

Specialized forms for consulting with VC funds (e.g., US, Arab World, EU) or business angels

- Training area: business plans, pitches, and international templates
- Networking area: workshops and seminars with investors
- Pitch verification

Synergistic actions among the various consultants involved enable a thorough evaluation of each project's maturity level and pre-money stage. This approach assists start-ups in identifying the most suitable financial instruments or types of investors based on their project characteristics and provides guidance during the initial phases of engagement with potential investors.

6. **Consultations with a Venture Capitalist:** These sessions aim to help participants:

- o gain a deeper understanding of market dynamics and the role of venture capitalists in fostering the success of innovative start-ups;
- o refine their business plans through a dedicated platform, thereby improving their ability to secure international funding;
- o find specialized support services. We engaged a consulting firm with proven expertise in supporting start-ups to deliver highly targeted services. The firm's role is to assess business potential, identify effective business models, support fundraising efforts by connecting start-ups with investors and assisting in pre-money valuations.

Alpimerchant S.r.l. was selected by UNITS to provide these services and will support up to 31 start-ups (all those involved in the acceleration phase of the first and second cycles). The planned activities include:

- One-to-one coaching sessions for all 31 start-ups, aimed at evaluating business potential and assisting them in rewriting their business plans according to the standard formats of three investment funds/venture capital operators to be selected under CC1. These formats will be shared in digital form through a dedicated CC1 start-up showcase.
- Selection of 5 “ready to scale-up” startups eligible to access the next phase through a transparent and objective process, with individual feedback provided to all startups.

For the five “ready-to-scale” start-ups, additional tailored activities are foreseen:

- a customized support program to further develop the business idea, taking into account each project's specific characteristics, and to define optimal fundraising strategies
- identification of three investment funds/venture capital operators potentially interested in each project, with support in adapting the business plan, including the financial plan and pre-money valuation, to meet their requirements
- organization of two individual meetings per start-up with potential investors and companies.

The consulting firm has already delivered one-to-one coaching sessions to the first-cycle start-ups, assessing their projects and providing individual feedback. However, not all of the contacted start-ups decided to move forward with this phase, despite efforts to highlight the value of this important opportunity.

Meetings with the second-cycle start-ups began right after the end of the acceleration phase (demo day held in Venice on 26 June 2025).

In addition, the selected company will actively participate in the final project event scheduled in Trieste on 18 September 2025.

7. **Final event:** The final CC1 event will be held on 18 September 2025 in Trieste and will serve as a showcase for the innovation ecosystem. It will bring together start-ups from both the first and second cycles of the iNEST project with leading Italian players in venture capital and early-stage investment. Its primary goal is to create a platform where innovative business ideas can meet potential funding partners, reinforcing the role of the program in bridging the gap between acceleration and market entry.

Formindustria FVG scarl has been appointed to manage the practical organization of the event.

The consulting company Alpimerchant S.r.l. is collaborating with UNITS to identify and engage investors to be invited to the event, leveraging its long-standing relationship with Italian Angels for Growth (IAG). In addition, Alpimerchant will ensure the on-site presence of its representatives to facilitate direct communication between start-ups and investors and to support the teams in effectively presenting their projects to attract potential funding.

Ongoing activities: The Spoke 8 members are currently closing the activity number 2 (meetings with banks) and are closing the public procedures of the remaining activities to be performed in 2025. They are organizing the final event, which will take place in Trieste on September 18, 2025. At this stage,

they are identifying and inviting a qualified audience composed of investors, mentors, and key industry stakeholders; representatives of venture capital funds and institutional actors; local companies and corporate venture capital operators; successful case studies able to share their experience and foster networking with the participating start-ups.

8.3. SPOKE 8 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

As part of the dissemination, one of the startups of the second acceleration cycle, Robotizr, was invited to join a lecture held by Dr. Chiara Marinelli of the master's degree course Entrepreneurship and Business Modeling of Prof. Guido Bortoluzzi. Robotizr's CEO Marco Bassoli was invited to present the startup case to the students during the lecture of April 2nd, 2025. The same course also hosted the business angel Carlo Asquini during the lecture of May 7th, 2025. Here, Dr. Asquini presented his experience as investor and as CEO of the company Alpimerchant S.r.l.

In addition, given the organizational needs for the final event and the student's interest for innovation management topics, we engaged the master's degree student Tatiana Zheliaskova to work hand-in-hand with Carlo Asquini and the CCI UniTS team. By December 2025, the student will present her master's thesis on her experience with the iNEST project and the project contribution to innovation in the North-East of Italy, with Prof. Guido Bortoluzzi as supervisor and the PhD student Chiara Marinelli as co-supervisor.

Moreover, the startup Robotizr had the opportunity to get in touch with five professors of other Departments of UniTS, who are active in engineering, AI and robotics. In her role as startup coach, Chiara Marinelli contributed to arrange online meetings and in-person visits in Trieste on May 22nd, 2025 for the CEO of the startup Marco Bassoli. The aim was to stimulate new win-win business and research collaborations with entities in the Friuli Venezia Giulia region for Robotizr.

8.4. SPOKE 8 CCI MAIN RESULTS

First and foremost, the wide range of CCI activities implemented within the framework of Spoke 8 has equipped participants with valuable tools to further develop and effectively present their entrepreneurial ideas.

Building on the lessons learned from the first-cycle start-ups, Spoke 8's scouting activities for the second cycle placed greater emphasis on research-driven and high-level initiatives. Consequently, the start-ups involved in the acceleration phase demonstrated higher levels of expertise and maturity, resulting in more solid and well-structured projects.

The initiatives organized during the fundraising phase provided additional key resources to strengthen and refine the quality of their business proposals. In particular, the one-to-one sessions with experts offered targeted guidance, enabling the start-ups to approach potential investors at the final event with greater preparation and an increased likelihood of securing funding.

The Spoke 8 CCI activities also fostered hands-on training through the involvement of UniTS PhD candidate Chiara Marinelli, who served as a start-up coach during the second-cycle acceleration program, coordinating with other coaches and holding weekly or bi-weekly meetings with the start-ups.

A key achievement of the second-cycle acceleration phase was the training and development of two UniTS–PoloAA start-ups throughout the entire program. Both successfully presented their projects during the final Pitch Day, with the SIPEOM project earning third place overall.

Finally, the need to create interdisciplinary educational materials and fully leverage the innovation potential of the collected entrepreneurial ideas has strengthened collaboration among the various stakeholders involved. This reinforced cooperation between diverse key actors has been instrumental in advancing the iNEST initiatives and fostering close, ongoing partnerships.

8.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

During the implementation of CCI activities, some operational challenges emerged.

During the coaching sessions of the 2nd Acceleration cycle there were some organizational hindrances due to the AcceleratorApp functioning. While the booking functionalities worked as expected, the videocall services were absent, which resulted in a progressive abandonment of its usage.

Concerning the Fundraising task, delays in the approval of the activity reorganization and budget reallocations - already highlighted in the previous update - required an adjustment of the original timeline. As a result, several fundraising-related activities had to be rescheduled and were eventually delivered jointly to start-ups from both the first and second cycles.

To ensure that second-cycle participants could fully benefit from the fundraising component, the sessions were postponed to late spring/beginning of summer, after they had completed the core acceleration phase and acquired the necessary business development tools. This delay, while operationally necessary, introduced an additional layer of complexity: the two cohorts presented different backgrounds, levels of maturity, and expectations. In response, the meeting agendas were redesigned to reflect the specific needs of each group, and trainers offered dedicated one-to-one sessions to address individual challenges and maximize learning outcomes.

Despite these efforts, participation in the introductory fundraising sessions was lower than expected. Some start-ups - particularly from the first cycle - expressed limited interest in continuing the program at that stage, either because they perceived their immediate priorities elsewhere or because their business models were not yet at a point where fundraising seemed relevant. Others reported difficulties in actively participating due to overlapping commitments. To mitigate the impact of reduced live participation, all sessions were recorded and made accessible for asynchronous consultation. This approach provided flexibility and ensured that key content remained available for future reference, even beyond the formal end of the program.

Similarly, some first-cycle start-ups did not take part to the one-to-one meetings with the specialized consulting firm. Recognizing the importance of individualized support, the consulting team made targeted efforts to re-engage the less active participants, highlighting how these tailored sessions could serve as a critical step in refining their business models and enhancing their investment readiness. Beyond providing technical guidance, the coaching aimed to foster a long-term strategic mindset, helping participants better position themselves for future funding opportunities and market expansion.

8.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

The next steps focus on completing the Fundraising phase and finalizing the program's closing activities.

In the coming weeks, the last sessions of the Fundraising track - dedicated to meetings with banking institutions - will be organized. Parallely, planning is underway for the remaining components, including the Meetings with Enterprises, the setup of the web-app platform, and the preparation of the closing events.

Particular attention is being given to the organization of the final CCI event, scheduled to take place in Trieste on 18 September 2025. This phase involves the identification and invitation of key venture capital firms and business angels whose participation will be critical to maximizing the event's impact and offering start-ups concrete funding opportunities.

9. SPOKE 9 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES within the Cross-Cutting Activity 1

The research activities of Spoke 9 address current issues in the sectors of mathematical and numerical models, scientific computing, and digital twins. These are supported and enhanced by four Research Topics (RTs), namely:

- **RT1 - Mathematical, Numerical and Data-driven Modeling**, which aims to create a framework for the mathematical modeling of complex systems, i.e. a mathematical description of systems composed of many interacting parts;
- **RT2 - Model Order Reduction**, an advanced numerical approach that is employed to reduce the computational cost of numerical simulations;
- **RT3 - Automatic Learning for Digital Twins**, devoted to the application of automatic learning techniques, such as machine learning and reduced order models, in a high-performance computing setting;
- **RT4 - Applications of DT in Industry, Medicine, Environmental Sciences, Daily life**, whose goal is to review the most updated techniques regarding the applications of digital twins to the environment, daily life, and infrastructures.

In this scientific context, **Cross-Cutting Activity 1** plays an important role in fostering a coordinated and transversal approach across all Spokes within the iNEST project. Aligned with the framework of an innovation ecosystem, this activity serves the purpose of valorizing innovative ideas arising from the research activities of Spoke 9 and facilitating the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs.

9.1. SPOKE 9 CC1 OBJECTIVES OVERVIEW

Within the iNEST Consortium, the overall goal of Cross-Cutting Activity 1 is to promote the generation and the selection of innovative ideas emerging from the scientific activities of Spoke 9 and to transform them into research start-ups and spin-offs. To this aim, CC1 is subdivided into four distinct phases.

The first phase of CC1 concerns the planning and the validation of all activities. This involved hiring dedicated personnel to support the activities as planned by the committee of the CC1.

Two start-up projects originally selected through the 1st Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed—**SINDREL** and **Sniff-nano**, both from SISSA—have reached the Fundraising phase; the objective of this phase is to help their team to contact Venture Capitalists and Business Angels who could support the further growth of these projects and their establishment as business realities. In this final phase, the management of the fundraising network is essential to collect all the possible funding possibilities and the partnership solutions. The founders will be supported with events and networking occasions with the aim of collecting financial resources and developing their business ideas. Leveraging the budget available under CC1 for start-up support, we will initiate collaborations with VeniSIA and Bio4Dreams to provide additional expertise, resources, and networking opportunities that accelerate the development of the startups' projects.

Meanwhile, the Acceleration phase of the 2nd cycle of CC1 has just concluded. The 2nd **Demo Day** of CC1 took place on June 26 in Venice. The only Spoke 9 start-up project that took part in the second Demo Day was **BIOXGEN**, which was presented as an early-stage project. BIOXGEN will likewise tap

into the CC1 start-up support budget to launch a collaboration with Bio4Dreams that will propel the advancement of its project.

9.2. SPOKE 9 CC1 TASKS AND ON-GOING ACTIVITIES

List of CC1 Tasks:

- CC1.1: Planning and validation
- **CC1.2: Pre-acceleration**
 - Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 9-40
 - Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 10-23
 - Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVE
Duration: months 12-26
 - Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. The objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs, and co-innovation activities between universities, startups, and companies.
Responsible: UNIUD
Duration: months 9-40
- CC1.3: Acceleration
 - Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 11-34
 - Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.
Responsible: UNIVR
Duration: months 14-40
 - Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. the objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.

Responsible: UNIVR
 Duration: months 15-32

- CC1.4: Fundraising

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 9

Background/State of the Art: For Task CC1.2, the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office supports Spoke 9 activities. Technology and knowledge transfer are considered crucial and strategic activities, and concrete and structured actions are taken systemically to promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, and improve the impact of the research results on society and the productive and economic ecosystem. For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.1**, the following figures followed Spoke 9 initiatives within CC1:

- Alberto Cavazza, who covered the role of Scouting Specialist for Spoke 9;
- Luca Mingotti Landriani, who covered the role of Event Communication Specialist (still holding the position);
- Sara Anzuinelli, who covered the role of Event Communication Assistant.

At the end of the 1st cycle of CC1, the Scouting Specialist and the Event Communication Assistant embarked on new professional and educational paths, making it necessary to replace these two roles. The person who covered the role of the Spoke 9 Scouting Specialist starting from January 16, 2025 is Luca Turconi.

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, the implementation of the Scouting Stage has consisted of preparing a Call for Start-up Pre-seed, one for each Spoke and each cycle of the activity. For Spoke 9, two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were prepared by the Scouting Specialist, under the supervision of the Scouting Officer and the Assistant Scouting Officers:

- The 1st Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in December 2023 and closed in February 2024;
- The 2nd Call for Start-up Pre-seed was opened in June 2024 and closed in September 2024.

Sub-task CC1.2.3 has been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

As for **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, an Open Innovation Day was held on January 30, 2025, in Padua, with the participation of about 40 innovative companies from Northeastern Italy. The event was aimed at consolidating the local innovation ecosystem, fostering joint open innovation between industries from Triveneto and universities and research institutes involved in iNEST.

Methodology: For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all the applications for the two Calls for Start-up Pre-seed were collected in a common database. Potential startupperes were contacted by the Scouting Specialist to organize a series of one-to-one meetings to explore together the potential of innovative ideas and research results to valorize. In this phase, the contribution of the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA has been recognized as fundamental, in particular to guide the Scouting Specialist to attract internal doctoral students and researchers potentially interested in proposing their ideas.

Start-up projects were then selected according to the Pre-acceleration funnel, which was designed by the Scouting Officer and his Assistants. The Pre-acceleration funnel consists of the following steps:

1. **Pre-screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.
2. **Screening.** It is performed by Scouting Specialists.

3. **Committee evaluation.** It is performed by the CC1 Committee.
4. **Selection Day.** During the Selection Day, all start-up projects from all Spokes that passed the Committee evaluation are presented to the CC1 Committee (and a possible external jury, in the case of the 2nd cycle). The Committee then selects about 10–15 teams for the Acceleration phase.
The Selection Day of the 1st cycle was held at the Luav University of Venice on March 19, 2024.
The Selection Day of the 2nd cycle was held at the University of Udine on December 3, 2024.

For **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, the innovative companies were selected by the Open Innovation Manager through a set of innovation performance indicators based on financial data, the number of patents held by the companies, and data on R&D and innovation projects funded through public calls. Companies with a turnover exceeding €50 million were considered.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, all activities described before are now over. For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, the activities following the Open Innovation Day are followed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 9

Background/State of the Art: Sub-task CC1.3.1 and **Sub-task CC1.3.2** have been developed by other Spokes and will not be treated hereon.

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, a centralized Acceleration program has been developed for the founders of the selected teams so that they can acquire all the knowledge and skills to build a solid business model. With a holistic approach to innovation that leverages synergies between academic research and the business world, the iNEST Accelerator aims to foster the creation of high-tech start-ups, generate skilled employment, and promote sustainable economic development in Northeastern Italy. Particular emphasis is placed on the preparation of a pitch, as each Acceleration cycle is closed by the Demo Day, a public event where start-up projects are presented to potential investors and professionals, offering significant networking opportunities and potential business collaborations. Start-up projects are evaluated by an external jury, and the most deserving teams are given an award.

Methodology: For **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, the Acceleration program has been structured with a series of in-person workshops, held by professionals involved in Cross-Cutting Activity 1 across the whole Triveneto region, which blend theory and practice in innovation and entrepreneurship. Pitch clinics, in which teams have the opportunity to try their pitch in front of a jury (either internal or external), are also part of the program. In the following, each of the two programs is detailed.

- 1st cycle:
 - Workshop #1: April 19–20, 2024, in Trieste (UniTS): “Strategy innovation and problem-client fit”.
 - Workshop #2: May 10–11, 2024, in Padua: “Solution and market fit”.
 - Workshop #3: May 31–June 1, 2024, in Trento: “Profit model” and a pitch session test.
 - Workshop #4: June 28–29, 2024, in Trieste (SISSA): “Go to market strategy”.
 - Workshop #5: August 30–31, 2024, in Verona: “Funding strategy”.
 - Pitch Clinic: September 20, 2024, in Venice.
- 2nd cycle:
 - Workshop #1: January 17–18, 2025, in Trento: “Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan”.

- Workshop #2: February 7–8, 2025, in Verona: “Problem, current solutions, and proposition”.
- Workshop #3: February 28–March 1, 2025, in Udine: “Market and competition”.
- Workshop #4: March 14–15, 2025, in Venice (Ca’ Foscari): “Governance, vision, mission, and strategy; Business Model”.
- Pitch Clinic #1: April 4, 2025, in Venice (Iuav).
- Workshop #5: May 9–10, 2025, in Bolzano: “Action plan & eco-fin plan”.
- Workshop #6: May 23–24, 2025, in Trieste: “Eco-fin plan & funding”.
- Pitch Clinic #2: June 6, 2025, in Verona.

Workshops are based on the lean startup methodology, which enables teams to test and adjust their hypotheses about solutions and markets quickly. This approach is particularly effective for technologies emerging from research, which require a clear and flexible commercialization path. Another essential component of the program is peer learning—participants learn from one another by sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions, accelerating their start-up's development.

Every start-up team is assigned two coaches, professionals from affiliated universities and institutions who help them apply what learned in workshops to their specific start-up contexts. Coaches follow start-up teams during the workshops and can also organize one-on-one coaching sessions.

The 1st cycle of the program also included five webinars, held by mentors—professionals from specific sectors who help all teams in a single field:

- Webinar #1: Presentation of psychological profiles (June 19, 2024) by Beniamino Mirisola;
- Webinar #2: Marketing, customer acquisition, sales (June 24, 2024) by Giacomo Tesolin;
- Webinar #3: IP strategy (July 5, 2024) by Elisa Toniolo;
- Webinar #4: Establishment of an innovative S.r.l. between civil and tax regulations (September 13, 2024) by Valter Carturo;
- Webinar #5: Innovative start-ups and contractual frameworks (September 27, 2024) by Paolo Guaragnella and Giorgio Abbadessa.

The 1st cycle of the activity was concluded by a Demo Day, held in Verona on October 25, 2024. A jury of 7 investors was featured: Augusto Coppola from Cloud Accelerator, Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Arianna Tibuzzi from Obloo Ventures, Michele Marcaccio from FNDX to represent Gellify, Tommaso Maschera from Plug and Play, Alessandro Nitti from CIV (Compagnia per l’Innovazione e i Valori), and Enrico Filì from CDP Venture Capital SGR.

For what concerns the 2nd Demo Day, held in Venice on June 26, 2025, a jury of 6 investors was featured: Alvisè Bonivento from Indaco Venture Partners Sgr, Bernardino D’Auria from Invitalia, Francesco De Michelis from MITO Technology, Francesco Rossi and Alberto Potycki from CDP Venture Capital Sgr, and Maria Claudia Pignata from VeniSIA.

Ongoing activities: As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, all activities are now over for the 2nd cycle as well.

Focus on Task CC1.4: Fundraising activities within Spoke 9

Background / State of the Art: The Fundraising phase (Task CC1.4) is designed to secure the financial resources that early-stage companies need to refine their products, grow their teams, and access the market. Within iNEST, Spoke 8 has already set up a structured calendar that mixes investor-facing events (1-to-1 sessions with venture capitalists), financial-literacy training (“Vocabolario del credito”), direct meetings with banks, and networking formats such as speed-dating and executive

round-tables with entrepreneurs. Tailored legal advice is also available on demand to help founders negotiate term-sheets and choose the right corporate framework.

Methodology:

- Central programme (Spoke 8) – Activities are delivered face-to-face across the Triveneto region and follow a funnel logic:
 - **Investor readiness:** group workshops that familiarise founders with VC language, credit instruments, and due-diligence requirements.
 - **Deal-making support:** curated introductions to venture capitalists and themed meetings with banks to match start-ups with the most suitable funding source.
 - **Networking acceleration:** speed dates with seasoned entrepreneurs to explore strategic partnerships and early-customer pilots.
 - **On-demand expertise:** a legal help-desk that founders can book for contract and IP issues.
- Spoke 9 integration – In parallel, Spoke 9 has carried out a scouting exercise to select external enablers that can be contracted through its dedicated CCI budget. Two specialised partners have been identified:
 - **VeniSIA** – to mentor SINDREL (1st cycle).
 - **Bio4Dreams** – to guide Sniff-Nano (1st cycle) and BIOXGEN (2nd cycle) in refining their deep-tech roadmaps, validating regulatory pathways, and structuring seed rounds.

Ongoing Activities:

- Spoke 8's common programme is underway: the Credit Vocabulary modules (May–June 2025), the four Bank meetings (May–July 2025), and the investor speed-dating sessions scheduled after the Demo Day of 26 June 2025.
- Within Spoke 9, contracts with VeniSIA and Bio4Dreams are being finalised; kick-off mentoring meetings are expected in Q3 2025, ensuring that SINDREL, Sniff-Nano, and BIOXGEN enter the Fundraising phase with a customised investor-outreach plan and sector-specific coaching.

An Investor Day is also being organized. This event will be aimed at presenting start-up projects of the 1st and 2nd cycle to a wide audience of selected investors.

9.3. SPOKE 9 CCI DISSEMINATION AND OTHER COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES

Focus on Task CC1.2: Scouting and Pre-acceleration activities within Spoke 9

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, to promote the application to the two Spoke 9 Calls for Start-up Pre-seed among doctoral students and researchers, two events have been organized at SISSA:

- iNEST Meet&Drink, held on January 17, 2024;
- iNEST: Ideas for Innovation, held on July 9, 2024.

During these events, iNEST and Cross-Cutting Activity 1 were presented by Spoke 9 and CCI representatives, and guidelines for preparing a good pitch were provided. For iNEST Meet&Drink, two SISSA start-up CEOs (Andrea Martini from FAST Computing and Enrico Siagri from MATERYS) were involved, so that they could provide insight into the entrepreneurial world to the aspiring innovators. For iNEST: Ideas for Innovation, instead, two Spoke 9 start-up co-founders involved in the 1st cycle of the program were involved, so that they could share their experience within the program and provide tips.

The opening of the two Calls and the promotion of these two events were disseminated through news articles (on the iNEST, Spoke 9, and SISSA websites), social media posts (SISSA LinkedIn and Facebook webpages), e-mails by the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office, and messages on students' internal chat groups. All these activities have been carried out with the help and the coordination of SISSA Press Office and SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office.

The two Selection Days were also publicly disseminated, through articles on the iNEST and Spoke 9 websites, and posts on the iNEST social media pages (LinkedIn and Facebook). The first Selection Day was also promoted with a YouTube video and two press releases (before and after the event), which were prepared with the aid of both the Ca' Foscari University and the Luav University of Venice Press Offices.

Finally, this phase of the activity has been described on the [iNEST](#) and [Spoke 9](#) websites, and the results of the 1st cycle were presented in a [dedicated webpage](#) and social media post.

For **Sub-task CC1.2.4**, the Open Innovation Day was disseminated with dedicated articles on the iNEST website and social media posts on the iNEST profiles. Moreover, a press release was prepared with the collaboration of the University of Padua and shared with the other Spokes in order to increase the visibility of the event. Finally, video interviews were filmed, featuring the main actors of the Open Innovation initiatives within iNEST, as well as the representatives of four companies (Carel Industries, FiloBlu, IRINOX, Thermokey) that participated in a round table during the event.

Focus on Task CC1.3: Acceleration activities within Spoke 9

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, both the 1st and the 2nd cycle of the Acceleration program have been publicly disseminated with a social media post on the iNEST accounts recapping every workshop and YouTube videos of each start-up project involved in the program (some videos of the 2nd cycle are yet to be published). For the 1st cycle, social media post was also prepared to promote the five webinars, and a dedicated section has been prepared on the [CC1 page](#) of the iNEST website.

In both cycles, the Demo Day has been promoted with a dedicated landing page on Eventbrite, a series of news articles on the iNEST website, and a number of social media posts on the iNEST accounts. For the 1st cycle, press releases, both for local newspapers and for online websites focusing on start-ups and innovation, have been published. The local press release has been prepared and disseminated with the aid of Press Offices from all universities involved in iNEST, particularly the University of Verona, whose members also conducted a video interview with relevant figures and start-ups. A number of articles concerning the start-up projects presented in the 1st Demo Day have been featured in local newspapers. Furthermore, all the key information concerning the start-up projects has been inserted in a dedicated booklet and in a [page on the iNEST website](#).

For the 2nd cycle, a press release focusing on the Demo Day has been prepared and published together with the Ca' Foscari University of Venice, and later shared with the other Spokes in order to increase visibility. The press release was sent together with a document featuring some in-depth information about each start-up participating in the event. A dedicated booklet was prepared as well.

9.4. SPOKE 9 CC1 MAIN RESULTS

For what concerns **Sub-task CC1.2.2**, **10** applications were registered in the 1st Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed, and **5** applications were registered in the 2nd Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed. These numbers were achieved both with the coordinated action of the Scouting Specialist and the SISSA Valorisation and Innovation Office, and with the two promotional events held at SISSA; in particular, 13 potential candidates were registered in iNEST Meet&Drink, whereas 12 potential candidates were registered in iNEST: Ideas for Innovation.

Following the Pre-acceleration funnel, ideas were then selected:

1. **Pre-screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of 10 applications for the Spoke 9 Call for Start-up Pre-seed, **5** ideas were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 11 applications, **6** ideas were admitted to the next selection step.
2. **Screening.** In the 1st cycle, out of 5 ideas from Spoke 9, **4** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 6 ideas from Spoke 9, **5** projects were admitted to the next selection step.
3. **Committee evaluation.**
In the 1st cycle, out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **4** were admitted to the next selection step.
In the 2nd cycle, out of 5 projects from Spoke 9, **4** were admitted to the next selection step.
4. **Selection Day.** Out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **2** have been admitted to the 1st Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.
Out of 4 projects from Spoke 9, **3** have been admitted to the 2nd Acceleration program, joining 13 teams from other Spokes.

As for **Sub-task CC1.3.3**, 15 start-up teams have participated in the 1st cycle of the program, and 11 have presented their pitch during the Demo Day, including both teams from Spoke 9. SINDREL was awarded as the best start-up project of the program, whereas Sniff-nano was awarded as the second-best start-up project of the program. For the 2nd cycle of the program, 3 Spoke 9 teams were supposed to be present: BIOXGEN, COCAL, and Easy Resp. However, Easy Resp later chose to withdraw from the programme. COCAL completed the full acceleration track but chose not to attend the second Pitch Clinic, and was therefore not admitted to the Demo Day.

For what concerns **task CC1.4**, activities are still in progress, and contracts with VeniSIA and Bio4Dreams are being finalised for SINDREL, Sniff-nano and BIOXGEN, respectively. COCAL was presented the opportunity to receive this kind of support but its team chose not to leverage it.

9.5. ENCOUNTERED PROBLEMS AND CORRECTIVE ACTIONS TAKEN

As for **Task CC1.2**, the main issue was the engagement of SISSA doctoral students and researchers, who are typically focused on basic research and pursue an academic path, being unaware of the possibilities of the entrepreneurial world. The two SISSA events helped to increase the number of applications, and another solution for the 2nd cycle was to scout ideas among researchers from the other Spoke 9 Affiliates. In this regard, the coordination with the Valorisation and Innovation Office of SISSA has also played an important role. By working together on procedures and methodologies, including the organization of the two SISSA events, it was possible to start a synergistic activity between the Valorisation and Innovation Office and the Scouting Specialist, who reported to Tanja Lunardelli, the figure dedicated to internal scouting in SISSA, the continuation of the activities, the response of the people met, and the potential issues to be addressed regarding the protection and patenting of ideas.

For what concerns **Task CC1.3**, the main issue encountered with the development of the 1st and the 2nd Acceleration program was to integrate diverse innovation fields and support teams from varied technological sectors while respecting the different timelines required to validate markets. Moreover, the Selection Day and the pitch trials brought up that, in some cases, it was not clear why some projects needed investments and how they could be best supported. With the help of workshops and coaching sessions, all the teams, and in particular Spoke 9 teams, developed a solid business model and learned how to valorize their strengths in front of potential investors.

Identifying interlocutors able to satisfy the very different fundraising needs of deep-tech life-science projects such as Sniff-Nano, SINDREL, and BIOXGEN proved harder than anticipated. After several rounds of scouting and exploratory meetings, however, two highly versatile partners were secured, VeniSIA and Bio4Dreams, whose complementary expertise and broad investor networks can collectively cover the full spectrum of requirements, ensuring that each start-up receives tailored, high-quality support.

9.6. NEXT STEPS AND CHALLENGES

With the beginning of the Fundraising phase, corresponding to **Task CC1.4**, the start-up projects of the 1st cycle are now meeting potential investors. On November 18, 2024, both Spoke 9 teams participated in a meeting with a Business Angel; on January 8, SINDREL was also involved in a meeting for the preparation of useful documentation and other tips. Valorizing these ideas and growing the business will be the main upcoming challenge for these start-up projects.

With the second acceleration cycle now concluded, the focus shifts entirely to Fundraising (Task CC1.4). Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico (Spoke 8) will extend its investor-readiness workshops, one-to-one matchmaking sessions, and legal clinics to the new cohort, ensuring that BIOXGEN and the other second-cycle teams benefit from the same support already offered to SINDREL and Sniff-Nano. In parallel, collaboration agreements with VeniSIA and Bio4Dreams are being activated: VeniSIA will mentor SINDREL, while Bio4Dreams will guide Sniff-Nano and BIOXGEN, providing all three ventures with sector-specific expertise and access to broad investor networks.

Moreover, Spoke 9 will maintain close interaction with the central iNEST Hub to help shape the forthcoming INEST2IMPACT initiative, which will build on the current programme's achievements and maximise their socio-economic impact across Northeastern Italy.

References

We report here the list of the links to the webpages relevant to Spoke 9 and in particular to Cross-Cutting Activity 1:

- [Spoke 9 website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the iNEST website](#)
- [Cross-Cutting Activity 1 page on the Spoke 9 website](#)
- [Results of the 1st cycle of CC1 \(page on the iNEST website\)](#)
- [Results of the 2nd cycle of CC1 \(page on the iNEST website\)](#)
- [List of news concerning CC1 on the iNEST website](#)